

**BUNDESMINISTERIUM
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Report 2011

**Trends and Sources of
Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents
in Humans, Foodstuffs, Animals and
Feedingstuffs**

Austria

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic agents and some
pathogenic microbiological agents**

AUSTRIA

The Report referred to in Article 9 of Directive 2003/99/EC

**TRENDS AND SOURCES OF ZONOSSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS
IN HUMANS, FOODSTUFFS, ANIMALS AND FEEDINGSTUFFS**

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks, antimicrobial
resistance in zoonotic agents and some pathogenic microbiological
agents**

IN 2011

1. Information on the Reporting and Monitoring System

Country: Austria

Reporting Year: 2011

This report was prepared by the Department for Statistics of the area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES. Following Institutions and Laboratories were involved:

Institutions and laboratories involved in monitoring

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
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Authorities

Central Veterinary Services	Federal Ministry of Health	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals; Revision of the draft of the Trend Report; Approval of the Trend Report for Submission
Food Office	Federal Ministry of Health	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
DG Public Health	Federal Ministry of Health	Validation of data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks; revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Feed Office	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, the Environment and Watermanagement	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Provincial Veterinary Services	9 provinces, one Veterinary Service per province	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals
Local/District health authorities	Part of each local administration authority ("Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde"), one physician per district	Collection and entry of the data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks

Institutes

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment (DSR)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Compilation, validation, preparation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report (Reporting officer, national reporter); Analysis of laboratory results for antimicrobial resistance of Salmonella spp., Campylobacter spp., Enterococcus faecalis/faecium and E. coli; Mapping of food and feed data; Creation of xml-files
Statistics Austria	The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions.	Demographic and livestock census data

Human Medicine

National Reference Centre for Salmonella Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Campylobacter, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of Campylobacter from food and animals, antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Testing for antimicrobial resistance of E. coli and enterococci from animals; data concerning MRSA
National Reference Centre for Tuberculosis, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in humans

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Center for E. coli including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Centre for Listeria Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Yersinia, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Toxoplasmosis, Echinococcosis, Toxocarosis and other Parasitic Diseases; Department of Medical Parasitology; Institute of Specific Prophylaxis and Tropical Medicine; Center for Physiology, Pathophysiology and Immunology	Medical University of Vienna	Laboratory data concerning parasitic diseases in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Clostridium difficile Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Analysis and Typing of Clostridium difficile from animals (and humans; not part of the report)

Food Control Institutes

Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs

Veterinary Medicine

National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in animals
National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Innsbruck	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning trichinellosis in animals
Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz and Moedling	Data concerning investigations in animals; bacteriological investigation in slaughtered animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in animals
Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Klagenfurt	Regional Veterinary Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in animals
Austrian Poultry Health Service (QGV)	Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. salmonella control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers	Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Feed Control Institute

Institute for Animal Nutrition and Feed, Linz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning feeding stuff
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PREFACE

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC1. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2011. The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in humans, animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and commensal bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks. Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given.

The information given covers zoonoses that are important for public health in the whole European Community as well as zoonoses which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the Community Legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual Community Summary Report on zoonoses that is published each year by EFSA.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
BMG	Federal Ministry of Health
BMSK	Federal Ministry for Social Security, Generations and Consumer Protection
CC-INFE	Competence Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology
EHEC	Enterohemorrhagic E. coli
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMS	Epidemiological Notification System for human notifiable diseases ("epidemiologisches Meldesystem")
ILMU	Official Food Control Laboratories, AGES
IMED	Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, AGES
IVET	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, AGES
MOH	Ministry of Health
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
OIE	World organisation for animal health
TESSy	the European Surveillance System
VIS	Veterinary Information System
VTEC	Verotoxin producing E. coli

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3. Animal Populations

3.1. Information on susceptible animal population

Sources of information

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria.

Herds, flocks, holdings, stocks

Cattle: The number of holdings and animals is based on the official database for cattle.

Equids, Pigs, Sheep, Goats and Farmed Deer: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey for pig, sheep and goats of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The number of holdings and animals is based on a random sample survey performed by Statistics Austria (farm structure survey). The last random sample survey was performed 2007.

Slaughters

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), combined with not-examined slaughters (out of pig-random-sample-surveys) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughters is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

Poultry: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly full survey in main poultry-slaughterhouses performed by Statistics Austria.

Dates the figures relate to and the content of the figures

Data are received from Statistics Austria, only poultry data from QGV.

Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the types covered by the information

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 147/2009 (Statistiken über den Viehbestand)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 291/2009 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Registrierungsverordnung 2009)

Poultry: BGBl. II Nr. 310/2007 (Erstellung der Statistik über die Agrarstruktur und den Viehbestand im Jahr 2007); BGBl. II Nr. 356/2003 (Erhebung der Geflügelschlachtungen in Betrieben mit min. 5000 Vorjahres-Geflügelschlachtungen)

Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings

Pigs: 97.15 % of all pigs are kept in 84.46 % of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 73.04 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 74.99 % of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 70.99 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 78.25 % of the goats are kept there.

Additional information

Nil

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of herds and holdings rearing animals, 2011 part 1

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of herds or flocks		Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
		n	Year	n	Year	n	Year	n	Year
Bovine animals	In total			69.586	01.12.2011	1.976.527	01.12.2011	688.489	2011
	LS: cattle under one year (incl. calves for slaughter) (slaughterings: calves only)					623.364	01.12.2011	73.336	2011
	Cows and heifers not for slaughtering purposes					1.069.384	01.12.2011	293.192	2011
	(mostly) Meat production animals (not incl. calves for slaughter)					283.779	01.12.2011	321.961	2011
	Mixed herds								
Sheep	In total*			16.374	01.04.2011	431.084	01.04.2011	287.790	2011
	Milk ewes			920	01.04.2011	24.260	01.04.2011		
	Meat production animals								
	Animals over 1 year (slaughtered as: sheep)			15.975	01.04.2011	248.995	01.04.2011	71.790	2011
	Animals under 1 year (slaughtered as: lambs)			13.308	01.04.2011	182.089	01.04.2011	216.000	2011
	Mixed herds								
Goats	In total*			10.901	01.04.2011	92.816	01.04.2011	53.930	2011
	Milk goats			2.706	01.04.2011	29.055	01.04.2011		
	Meat production animals								
	Animals over 1 year (slaughtered as: goats)			10.649	01.04.2011	62.876	01.04.2011	12.147	2011
	Animals under 1 year (slaughtered as: kids)			4.545	01.04.2011	29.940	01.04.2011	41.783	2011
Mixed herds									
Pigs	In total			31.726	01.04.2011	3.097.253	01.04.2011	5.601.002	2011
	Sows and gilts (slaughterings: sows only)			7.546	01.04.2011	277.625	01.04.2011	100.609	2011
	Fattening pigs			24.075	01.04.2011	1.124.569	01.04.2011	5.500.393	2011
	Breeding animals								
	Multiplication animals								
	Mixed herds								
Gallus gallus	In total (slaughterings: in major slaughterhouses only)							72.558.000	
	Breeding animals in total	127		65		1.060.420			
	Breeding animals for egg production line in total	24		11		242.926			
	Breeding animals for meat production line in total	103		54		817.494			
	Elite birds in total	0						0	
	Elite birds for egg production line	0							
	Elite birds for meat production line	0							
	Grandparent birds in total	0							
	Grandparent birds for egg production line	0							
	Grandparent birds for meat production line	0							
	Parent birds in total	127		65		1.060.420			n.a
	Parent birds for egg production line	24		11		242.926			n.a
	Parent birds for meat production line	103		54		817.494			n.a
Laying hens	2.843		1.104		8.534.756			n.a	
Broilers	3.500		464		57.675.723				
Mixed flocks/ holdings									

* Some holdings keep sheep and goats together. Thus the sum of holdings in total with sheep and goats amounts to 24.216.

Table 2 Susceptible animal populations: number of herds and holdings rearing animals, 2011 part 2

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of herds or flocks		Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
		n	Year*	n	Year*	n	Year*	n	Year*
Turkey	In total (slaughters: in slaughterhouses only)	340		126		2.301.953		protected	
	Breeding animals in total							0	
	Elite birds							0	
	Grandparent birds							0	
	Parent birds							0	
	Meat production birds	340		126		2.301.953		protected	
	Mixed flocks/ holdings								
Geese	In total (slaughters: in slaughterhouses only; incl. ducks)							protected	
	Breeding animals in total								
	Elite birds							0	
	Grandparent birds							0	
	Parent birds							0	
	Meat production animals								
	Mixed flocks/ holdings							n.a.	
Ducks	In total (slaughters: part of geese)							protected	
	Breeding animals in total								
	Elite birds							0	
	Grandparent birds							0	
	Parent birds							0	
	Meat production animals								
	Mixed flocks/ holdings								
Equids				15.257	01.04.2011	73.202	01.04.2011	1.003	2011
Farmed deer				1.577	01.04.2011	35.661	01.04.2011		
Farmed reindeers									
Farmed wild boars									

4. Information on Specific Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents

The World Health Organization defines zoonoses as “those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man.” Foodstuffs often serve as vehicles of zoonotic infections. Zoonotic agents include viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites or other biological entities that are likely to cause zoonoses.

Collection of human cases

Starting with January 1st 2009 a new reporting system, the **epidemiological reporting system** (Epidemiologisches Meldesystem, EMS) has been put in operation at the MOH. The physicians report all notifiable diseases (case based) to the local health authorities which are part of the local administration authorities (“Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde”). The physicians working at the local health authorities (public health officers) have to enter the data of the human cases of all notifiable diseases in the data base EMS including all relevant variables and laboratory results (case based). In the near future all laboratories will enter the results of their laboratory work in EMS via a gateway to streamline the process. Beginning with 2011 the national reference laboratories dealing with zoonotic diseases already enter their laboratory data in EMS.

EMS is the one and only database for notifiable diseases in the human sector in Austria. This system is also the standard gateway for reporting to ECDC (TESSy). A short report is also extracted and compiled using EMS which is published nationwide monthly and once a year by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMG-homepage:
(http://bmg.gv.at/home/Schwerpunkte/Krankheiten/Uebertragbare_Krankheiten/Statistiken/Monatliche_Statistik_meldepflichtiger_Infektionskrankheiten_ab_2010).

Additionally data of primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centres are available. The responsible reference centres for zoonotic diseases published the numbers of microbiologically typed primary isolates from humans; due to the fact that more than one bacterial strain could be isolated from single patients these figures may differ from the case numbers notified to the Federal Ministry. As mentioned above, with 2011 these laboratory data are also available in the EMS.

In this report it is indicated which data source has been used for the reporting of human cases for each respective zoonosis.

General Information about the Food Sampling Strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2010 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2011“ (BMG-75500/0194-II/2010) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can

comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2011, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production. In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-dept information. In 2011, nine food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0195-II/B/13/2010). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

4.1. Salmonellosis

4.1.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human salmonellosis remains a major health problem in Austria. In 2010, the number of notified salmonellosis cases was the second highest reported pathogen after campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. The salmonella-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30% in 1999 to less than 5.5% in 2011. The consumption of eggs and egg products that are contaminated with Salmonella is presumably the main cause of human infection.

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report (table 2) reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella, n = 2,193. This number shows again a reduction compared to the previous year and reflects the success of interventions aimed at combating salmonella.

As compared to the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis (see chapter campylobacteriosis), salmonella is the second most important cause for enteric diseases in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2011, data from feedingstuffs (n = 491; only feedingstuffs for food producing animals, exclusive pet feed) indicate that the prevalence of salmonella (< 1%) remains very low. None of the tested table eggs (85 samples, between 25 g and 360 g tested) were positive for salmonella, although infected eggs pose the main vehicle for human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

There were EU programs implemented to control the contamination of Salmonella in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks according to EU legislation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started, especially to improve harmonization of monitoring and control programs along the food chain.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obligated to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

4.1.2. Salmonellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory cases (food borne, non-food borne, and asymptomatic cases) confirmed in the National Reference Centre for Salmonella.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following four symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Fever
- Abdominal pain
- Vomiting

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of Salmonella (other than *S. Typhi* and *S. Paratyphi*) from stool or blood

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Sample material is processed as described in „Richtlinien für die Diagnostik von Salmonellen (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 11-12)“.

At the National Reference Centre for Salmonella (NRC Salmonella), all isolates are serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. And further all *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK. Additionally the antimicrobial resistance testing by disk diffusion method is performed with each isolate.

Notification system in place

Notification of salmonellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 1989 and 1990, human infections with salmonella increased markedly in Austria. After a peak in 1992, the incidence of salmonella illness decreased, but the number of infections has remained at a high level until 2002. Since that year the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human Salmonella infections has decreased by 73% (2011: 2,193 laboratory confirmed cases by the National Reference Centre for Salmonella).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2011, the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human Salmonella infections decreased compared to the year before (2,209 cases in 2010; 2,775 cases in 2009).

The proportion of *S. Enteritidis*, out of all Salmonella isolates, remained in 2011 at about the same level at 57% (compared to 55% in 2010). The most frequently identified phage types in 2011 were: PT8 (40%), PT4 (16%), PT21 (13%) and PT6 (12%). The reduction of salmonellosis cases is only due to *S. Enteritidis*, all other serotypes remained more or less constant between 1,200 and 947 cases (2002 to 2011).

The number of *S. Typhimurium* cases reported increased minor in absolute numbers (2011: 291 cases; 2010: 248; 2009: 482) and in relative numbers: 13% compared to 11.2% in 2010. Additionally 70 cases

were caused by *S. Typhimurium* monophasic strain; according to the new classification those strains also have to be added to *S. Typhimurium*, therefore the overall number of cases caused by *S. Typhimurium* is 361.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2011, the number of notified human cases of campylobacteriosis again exceeded the number of salmonellosis cases. The reduction in the number of human salmonellosis cases is due to EU wide control programs and establishment of goals for the reduction of prevalences of salmonella in laying hen flocks, broilers and turkeys.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH

Table 3 Salmonellosis cases (food borne, non-food borne, and asymptomatic cases) in humans - serotype distribution, 2011 (NRC)

	Cases	Incidence/100,000	Imported cases	Unknown status
Salmonellosis	2,193	26,1	65	2128
<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	1246	14,8	36	1210
<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	291	3,5	5	286
of these: DT 104L MR	38	0,5		38
monophasic <i>S. Group B</i> (1,4,5,12 : i : -)	73	0,9	2	71
<i>S. Stanley</i>	71	0,8	2	69
<i>S. Infantis</i>	68	0,8	1	67
<i>S. Bovismorbificans</i>	36	0,4		36
<i>S. Braenderup</i>	26	0,3	1	25
<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	25	0,3	1	24
<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	22	0,3		22
<i>S. Paratyphi B var. Java</i>	20	0,2		20
<i>S. Thompson</i>	19	0,2		19
<i>S. Coeln</i>	18	0,2		18
<i>S. Newport</i>	16	0,2	1	15
<i>S. Hadar</i>	14	0,2		14
<i>S. Brandenburg</i>	13	0,2		13
<i>S. Agona</i>	13	0,2		13
<i>S. Kentucky</i>	13	0,2		13
<i>S. Virchow</i>	13	0,2	2	11
<i>S. Corvallis</i>	11	0,1	1	10
<i>S. Kottbus</i>	11	0,1		11
other serotypes	174	2,1	13	164

Data source: NRC as of April 30, 2012

Table 4 Salmonellosis cases (food borne, non-food borne, and asymptomatic cases) in humans - age distribution, 2011

Age group	Salmonellosis			S. Enteritidis			S. Typhimurium			monophasic S. Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -)			other serotypes*		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	25	17	8	11	7	4	5	4	1	1	1		8	5	3
1 to 4 years	315	179	134	180	101	78	44	27	17	11	6	5	80	45	34
5 to 14 years	405	216	186	272	149	122	56	26	29	13	7	6	64	34	29
15 to 24 years	279	124	153	149	66	82	30	14	16	9	4	5	91	40	50
25 to 44 years	467	246	216	234	121	110	48	26	22	12	6	6	173	93	78
45 to 64 years	358	185	172	209	100	109	51	35	16	15	5	10	83	45	37
65 years and older	325	138	186	184	75	108	56	25	31	12	10	2	73	28	45
Age unknown	19	7	11	7	1	6	1		1				11	6	4
All age groups	2,193	1,112	1,066	1,246	620	619	291	157	133	70	37	33	586	298	281

* without SE, ST und monophasic S. Group B

Data source: NRC as of April 30, 2012

Table 5 Salmonellosis cases (food borne, non-food borne, and asymptomatic cases) in humans – seasonal distribution, 2011

	<i>Salmonella sp.</i>	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	monophasic S. Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -)	other serotypes*
Month	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases
January	101	38	29	3	31
February	70	23	22	1	24
March	109	28	30	7	44
April	82	41	11	2	28
May	134	85	15	3	31
June	231	153	17	5	56
July	260	171	36	5	48
August	359	237	45	19	58
September	360	188	41	14	117
October	267	172	19	9	67
November	111	60	14	2	35
December	109	50	12	3	44
not known					
Total	2,193	1,246	291	73	583

* without SE, ST und monophasic S. Group B

Data source: NRC as of April 30, 2012

4.1.3. Salmonella spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2011 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2011“ (BMG-75500/0194-II/2010) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2011, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2011, nine food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0195-II/B/13/2010). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to ISO 6579: 1999, with modifications: After preenrichment, selective enrichment in modified semisolid Rappaport-Vassiliadis or Diasalm, 18-24 hours at 42°C. Subsequently plating on XLD agar, Brilliant green-Phenolred-Lactose-Saccharose agar (BPLS), Salmonella Detection and Identification Medium (SMID) or Rambach agar.

25 g of raw material for egg products or 25 g of pooled content of 5 table eggs are either incubated directly or preenriched in peptone water. Further steps are performed as described above.

All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage-typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh single broiler meat samples in 7% (27 out of 384), in 7.1% of fresh turkey meat samples (3 out of 42), and in 28 out of 232 samples (12.1 %) of meat preparation from broilers, intended to be eaten cooked. None of the 301 mixed red meat samples (fresh and cooked meat) were tested positive. In all the pig meat samples (fresh and cooked), 3 of the 1,309 tested single samples (0.2%) were found positive. No positive samples were found in other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods in campaign A-022-11: 46 samples tested and in campaign A-030-11: 78 samples tested; in fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat – chilled (A-042-11) none out of the 34 samples tested positive; out of the 86 samples of infant formula - dried (campaign A-002-11) none of them tested positive for *Salmonella*. In 2011, 936 samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cows', sheeps' or goats' milk) were tested for *Salmonella* spp. and no sample was found positive as in the years 2007 -

2010. Out of the 85 sample units, each containing 25g of table eggs that were sampled and examined at packing centres or at retail level, no sample was tested positive for salmonella.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-002-11: Salmonella spp. in food – infant formula - dried - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January - March

Type of specimen taken

infant formula - dried

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

86 samples tested, 0-time positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Enterobacter sakazakii

Campaign A-013-11: Salmonella spp. in food – Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - dried dietary foods for special medical purposes intended for infants below 6 months - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: February - March

Type of specimen taken

Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - dried dietary foods for special medical purposes intended for infants below 6 months

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

21 samples tested, 0-time positive for Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-018-11: Salmonella spp. in food – Juice - mixed juice - unpasteurised - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: March - June

Type of specimen taken

Juice - mixed juice - unpasteurised

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

102 samples tested, 0-time positive for Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-022-11: Salmonella spp. in food – Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

46 samples tested, 0-time positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Listeria monocytogenes and VTEC

Campaign A-030-11: Salmonella spp. in food – Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - August

Type of specimen taken

Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

78 samples tested, 0-time positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Listeria monocytogenes

Campaign A-042-11: Salmonella spp. in food – Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - October

Type of specimen taken

Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat – chilled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

34 samples tested, 0-time positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Listeria monocytogenes

Table 6 Salmonella spp. in poultry meat and meat products, 2011

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Abony	Salmonella - S. Bredeney	Salmonella - S. Coelh	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	Salmonella - S. Hadar	Salmonella - S. Indiana	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Kentucky	Salmonella - S. Saintpaul	Salmonella - S. Stanley	Salmonella - S. Virchow
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		11	2							2				
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		55	3							3				
				10 g		1	0											
		IT	single	25 g		3	0											
		XX	single	25 g		2	1							1				
		DE	single	25 g		18	0											
		HU	single	25 g		1	1							1				
		FR	single	25 g		1	0											
		HR	single	25 g		1	0											
	LT	single	25 g		1	0												
at slaughterhouse	AT	single	25 g		10	0												
Unknown	AT	single	25 g		280	20			3	1		1	11	1	3			
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		232	28						26	1			1	
Meat from duck - fresh	at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0											
		HU	single	25 g		2	0											
		FR	single	25 g		1	0											
Meat from duck - meat products	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		3	0											
Meat from geese - fresh	at processing plant	HU	single	25 g		1	0											
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0											
		HU	single	25 g		2	1	1										
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		5	0											
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		6	1							1				
		XX	single	25 g		2	0											
		HU	single	25 g		1	0											
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		4	0											
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		91	9	1	1					2	1	3		1
				10 g		1	0											
		XX	single	25 g		2	0											
		DE	single	25 g		10	0											
		HU	single	25 g		1	0											
		BR	single	25 g		1	0											
RO	single	25 g		1	0													
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	AT	single	25 g		8	0											
		XX	single	25 g		1	0											
		DE	single	25 g		3	0											
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0											
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		5	0											
				50 g		1	0											
		DE	single	25 g		3	0											
Meat from turkey - fresh	at retail	AT	single	25 g		33	3					1		1		1		
		IT	single	25 g		2	0											
		XX	single	25 g		1	0											
		DE	single	25 g		3	0											
		HU	single	25 g		1	0											
	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		2	0											
Meat from turkey - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		3	0											

Table 7 Salmonella spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2011 part 1

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Kentucky	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		1	0				
		XX	single	25 g		1	0				
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		4	0				
				25 g		11	0				
		XX	single	25 g		1	0				
	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		3	0				
	Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single	10 g		10	0			
25 g						1	0				
DE			single	10 g		1	0				
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		3	0				
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Unknown	AT	single	10 g		5	0				
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		1	0				
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		19	0				
				25 g		3	0				
		XX	single	10 g		1	0				
		DE	single	10 g		1	0				
	at slaughterhouse	AT	single	10 g		1	0				
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		3	0				
				25 g		1	0				
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		28	1			1	
				25 g		2	0				
				DE	single	10 g		1	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		33	0				
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0				
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - chilled	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0				
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - chilled	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0				
Meat from pig - fresh	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0				
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		6	0				
				25 g		17	0				
		XX	single	10 g		1	0				
				25 g		3	0				
	DE	single	25 g		1	0					
Unknown	AT	single	10 g		178	1		1			
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		9	0				
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0				
	at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		7	0				
				25 g		2	0				
		XX	single	25 g		2	0				
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		141	1			1	
				25 g		19	0				
		XX	single	10 g		2	0				
DE	single	10 g		5	0						

Table 8 Salmonella spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2011 part 2

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Kentucky	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	AT	single	10 g		1	0				
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		2	0				
				25 g		8	0				
	Unknown	AT	single	10 g		508	2	1		1	
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	0				
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Unknown	AT	single	10 g		786	1		1		
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single	10 g		2	0				
				25 g		1	0				
Meat from sheep - fresh	at border control	AU	single	25 g		1	0				
	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		1	0				
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		1	0				
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		5	0				
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		5	0				
		XX	single	25 g		1	0				
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		101	0				
				25 g		7	0				
		XX	single	10 g		1	0				
		DE	single	10 g		3	0				
at slaughterhouse	AT	single	10 g		1	0					
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)	at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0				
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	at catering	AT	single	25 g		2	0				
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		8	0				
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		53	0				
		IT	single	25 g		4	0				
		ES	single	25 g		1	0				
		DE	single	25 g		8	0				
		HU	single	25 g		1	0				
FR	single	25 g		1	0						
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	AT	single	25 g		4	0				
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		8	0				
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		46	0				
		XX	single	25 g		1	0				
		DE	single	25 g		2	0				
		SI	single	25 g		4	0				
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0				
	at game handling est	AT	single	25 g		1	0				
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		18	0				
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		66	0				
		IT	single	25 g		10	0				
		ES	single	25 g		4	0				
		DE	single	25 g		8	0				
		SI	single	25 g		4	0				
		HU	single	25 g		5	0				
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		2	0				
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		32	0				
				25 g		4	0				
		DE	single	10 g		1	0				

Table 9 Salmonella spp. in milk and dairy products, 2011 part 1

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Cheeses made from cows' milk - curd	at retail	AT	single	25 g		6	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		11	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0
		CY	single	25 g		1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		4	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		12	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	
		IE	single	25 g		1	0
		IT	single	25 g		1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		20	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		11	0
		DE	single	25 g		1	0
		IT	single	25 g		1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		73	0
	at retail	FR	single	25 g		1	0
		AT	single	25 g		8	0
		CH	single	25 g		1	0
		DE	single	25 g		2	0
		IT	single	25 g		4	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		14	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		35	0
				50 g		1	0
		IT	single	25 g		2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	25 g		12	

Table 10 Salmonella spp. in milk and dairy products, 2011 part 2

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		11	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		6	0
		DK	single	25 g		1	0
		GR	single	25 g		1	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		4	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		5	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		3	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		4	0
		XX	single	25 g		1	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		2	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		7	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		3	0
	at retail	GR	single	25 g		3	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at retail	FR	single	25 g		1	0
		AT	single	25 g		4	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		2	0
	at retail	DE	single	25 g		3	0
		HU	single	25 g		1	0
		IT	single	25 g		1	0
		SK	single	25 g		1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
		DE	single	25 g		2	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		9	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		25	0
		PL	single	25 g		1	0
		SI	single	25 g		1	0
		SK	single	25 g		1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	

Table 11 Salmonella spp. in milk and dairy products, 2011 part 3

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk	at catering	AT	single	25 g		30	
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		15	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts - chilled	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at border control	IL	single	25 g		1	0
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		36	0
	at retail	FR	single	25 g		1	0
		AT	single	25 g		17	0
	DE	single	25 g		2	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	at retail	AT	single	25 g		11	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		40	0
	at retail	FR	single	25 g		1	0
		AT	single	25 g		328	0
		CH	single	25 g		1	0
		DE	single	25 g		7	0
		IT	single	25 g		1	0
XX	single	25 g		7	0		
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	
Milk from other animal species or unspecified	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
		XX	single	25 g		1	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		23	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		6	0
		XX	single	25 g		1	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at farm	AT	single	25 g		6	0
		XX	single	25 g		2	0
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		5	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		10	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at farm	AT	single	25 g		9	0
		XX	single	25 g		1	0
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		6	0
at retail	AT	single	25 g		8	0	
Milk, goats' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	
Milk, sheep's - raw	at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0

Table 12 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2011 part 1

Food	Sampling details	sampStage	sampOrig	sampUnit	sampWeight	sampWeightUnit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	Salmonella - S. Kentucky	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka
Bakery products		at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		5	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		6	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			BA	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
TR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0			
Bakery products - cakes		at retail	AT	single	25 g		85	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - cakes - containing heat-treated cream		at catering	AT	single	25 g		27	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - pastry		at catering	AT	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		103	0	0	0	0
					50 g		4	0	0	0	0
			IT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			GR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			JP	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			TW	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Beverages, alcoholic - wines		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	
Beverages, non-alcoholic		at retail	TW	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	
Cereals and meals		at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	
Chocolate		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		7	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		18	0	0	0	0
			IT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		5	0	0	0	0
			FR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			CH	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			BE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		15	0	0	0	0
			XX	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			CH	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			TR	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			IN	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			ZA	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Confectionery products and pastes		at catering	AT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	
Crustaceans		at border control	XX	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
		at processing plant	IT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			IT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single	25 g		7	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		5	0	0	0	0
			NL	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			FR	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			TH	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			VN	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			DK	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			CL	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			CN	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			IS	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
NZ	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0			
Crustaceans - unspecified - cooked		at catering	AT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	
Egg products		at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			NL	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			GL	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			BE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Egg products - dried		at retail	AR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	
Egg products - liquid		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		10	1	1	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			IT	single	25 g		4	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			NL	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Eggs		at packing centre	AT	single	25 g		5	0	0	0	0
		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		13	0	0	0	0

Table 13 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2011 part 2

Food	Sampling details	sampStage	sampOrig	sampUnit	sampWeight	sampWeightUnit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	Salmonella - S. Kentucky	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka	
Eggs - table eggs	at packing centre	AT	single	25 g	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				180 g	2	0	0	0	0	0		
				300 g	4	0	0	0	0	0		
				360 g	3	0	0	0	0	0		
		at retail	AT	single	25 g	24	0	0	0	0	0	0
					180 g	4	0	0	0	0	0	
					300 g	29	0	0	0	0	0	
					360 g	1	0	0	0	0	0	
	XX	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			300 g	3	0	0	0	0	0			
			240 g	1	0	0	0	0	0			
			ES	single	300 g	1	0	0	0	0		
	DE	single	25 g	3	0	0	0	0	0			
			300 g	2	0	0	0	0	0			
	FR	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0	0			
			AT	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0		
Fish - raw	at retail	XX	single	25 g	2	0	0	0	0			
		XX	single	25 g	2	0	0	0	0			
Fishery products, unspecified	at catering	XX	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
		AT	single	25 g	3	0	0	0	0			
	at retail	XX	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
		DE	single	25 g	2	0	0	0	0			
Fishery products, unspecified - non-ready-to-eat - chilled	at catering	AT	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
Fishery products, unspecified - non-ready-to-eat - frozen	at catering	AT	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled	at catering	AT	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
	campaign A-042-11	at retail	AT	single	25 g	34	0	0	0	0		
Fishery products, unspecified - seafood pate	at catering	AT	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - dried dietary foods for special medical purposes intended for infants below 6 months	campaign A-013-11	at retail	AT	single	25 g	21	0	0	0	0		
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g	2	0	0	0	0			
		at retail	AT	single	25 g	8	0	0	0			
		DE	single	25 g	6	0	0	0	0			
		PE	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
Fruits	at retail	AT	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
Fruits - products	at retail	AT	single	50 g	2	0	0	0	0			
Infant formula	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g	5	0	0	0	0			
		at retail	AT	single	25 g	20	0	0	0			
		XX	single	25 g	2	0	0	0	0			
		DE	single	25 g	9	0	0	0	0			
Infant formula - dried	campaign A-002-11	at retail	AT	single	25 g	86	0	0	0			
Juice - fruit juice	at retail	AT	single	25 g	4	0	0	0	0			
		NL	single	25 g	5	0	0	0	0			
		FR	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
		GB	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
Juice - fruit juice - pasteurised	at retail	AT	single	25 g	20	0	0	0	0			
Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
	at retail	AT	single	25 g	14	0	0	0	0			
Juice - mixed juice	at retail	AT	single	25 g	3	0	0	0	0			
		DE	single	25 g	1	0	0	0	0			
Juice - mixed juice - unpasteurised	campaign A-018-11	at retail	AT	single	25 g	102	0	0	0			
Juice - vegetable juice - unpasteurised	at feed mill	AT	single	25 g	3	0	0	0	0			

Table 14 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2011 part 3

Food	Sampling details	sampStage	sampOrig	sampUnit	sampWeight	sampWeightUnit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	Salmonella - S. Kentucky	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka		
Live bivalve molluscs		at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation		at game handling est	AT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0		
		at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	0	0	0	0		
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0		
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		11	0	0	0	0		
			IT	single	25 g		4	0	0	0	0		
Molluscan shellfish - raw		at catering	AT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0		
Mushrooms		at retail	XX	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0		
			ES	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
			DE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
Nuts and nut products		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
			XX	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
			DE	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0		
			TR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
			ID	single	25 g		6	0	0	0	0		
Other food		at catering	AT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0		
		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		10	1	0	1	0		
		at retail	XX	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
						25 g		50	0	0	0		
						50 g		1	0	0	0		
			GR	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0		
		XX	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0			
		DE	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0			
		Other food of non-animal origin		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		9	0	0	0	0
				at retail	TR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
AT	single				25 g		4	0	0	0	0		
IT	single				25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
DE	single				25 g		4	0	0	0	0		
imported product	at retail	XX	single	25 g		7	0	0	0	0			
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		at catering	AT	single	25 g		26	0	0	0	0		
						50 g		11	0	0	0		
			XX	single	25 g		6	0	0	0	0		
		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		5	0	0	0	0		
						50 g		3	0	0	0		
		at retail	AT	single	10 g		2	0	0	0	0		
						25 g		317	0	0	0		
						50 g		247	1	1	0		
			IT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
			GR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
			XX	single	25 g		26	0	0	0	0		
						50 g		3	0	0	0		
			DE	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0		
						50 g		3	0	0	0		
			NL	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
						50 g		1	0	0	0		
			HR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
			CH	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
			DK	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
		TW	single	50 g		1	0	0	0	0			
		BE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0			
		ZA	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0			
		CN	single	50 g		1	0	0	0	0			
		US	single	50 g		1	0	0	0	0			
		Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		39	0	0	0	0
				at retail	AT	single	25 g		59	0	0	0	
							34	0	0	0			
IT	single				25 g		6	0	0	0			
DE	single	25 g		11	0	0	0						
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta/rice salad		at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0		
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods	campaign A-022-11	at retail	AT	single	25 g		46	0	0	0	0		
	campaign A-030-11	at retail	AT	single	25 g		78	0	0	0	0		

Table 15 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2011 part 4

Food	Sampling details	sampStage	sampOrig	sampUnit	sampWeight	sampWeightUnit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	Salmonella - S. Kentucky	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka
Ready-to-eat salads		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		29	0	0	0	0
			XX	single	25 g		4	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		37	0	0	0	0
			IT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		9	0	0	0	
Sauce and dressings		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise		at catering	AT	single	25 g		6	0	0	0	0
		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
Seeds, dried		at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			TR	single	25 g		0	1	0	0	1
			BE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			LB	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			UG	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Soups - dehydrated	imported product	at retail	XX	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	
Spices and herbs		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		7	0	0	0	0
			XX	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			TR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		96	0	0	0	0
			IT	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			XX	single	25 g		13	0	0	0	0
			ES	single	25 g		4	0	0	0	0
			DE	single	25 g		36	0	0	0	0
			HU	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			EG	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			NL	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			FR	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			TH	single	25 g		6	0	0	0	0
			VN	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			HR	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
			IL	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0
			TR	single	25 g		12	0	0	0	0
			IN	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0
			CN	single	25 g		6	0	0	0	0
GB	single	25 g		3	0	0	0	0			
ID	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0			
CZ	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0			
EE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0			
GT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0			
LK	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0			
MG	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	0			
TN	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0			
Spices and herbs - dried - non-irradiated		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	
Sweets		at retail	AT	single	25 g		31	0	0	0	
			XX	single	25 g		2	0	0	0	
			DE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	
Vegetables		at border control	XX	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		4	0	0	0	
			IT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	
Vegetables - pre-cut - ready-to-eat		at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	
Vegetables - products		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		5	0	0	0	
			XX	single	50 g		1	0	0	0	
Vegetables - products - canned		at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	

4.1.4. Salmonella spp. in animals

A. Salmonella spp. in Gallus gallus - breeding flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities.

If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

If a parent flock tests positive for other salmonella serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimise biosecurity.

Frequency of the sampling

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Every flock is tested at day one

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and 2 weeks before the laying period starts.
2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive Salmonella test results then follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Monitoring by national program, takes place at hatchery, each flock is tested every two weeks at hatch by the farmer, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; additionally each flock is tested every 4 weeks by the farmer by boot swabs.

Type of specimen taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)**Production period**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: Drag swabs, pooled faeces and dust in the hatchery, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)**Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)****Day-old chicks**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)**Rearing period**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 60 pooled droppings a 1 gram per flock, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks: Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 1 drag swab, pooled faeces, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Case definition**Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)****Day-old chicks**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: Salmonella spp. isolated from hatcher basket liners

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)**Rearing period**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from 5 pairs of boot swaps or 300 faeces samples.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)**Production period**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from 5 pairs of boot swaps or 300 faeces samples.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used**Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)****Day-old chicks**

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: See day old chicks

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: See day old chicks

Vaccination policy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against Salmonella Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). The Austrian program for monitoring and eradication of Salmonella in breeding flocks of poultry was again (already since 2000) approved for the year 2006 by Commission Decision 2005/887/EG of 12 December 2005.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation:

- Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding
- Culling of the infected flock
- Disposal of the hatched eggs
- Abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection
- If necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2011, *Salmonella* spp. was detected in two parent flocks in Austria. Only one flock was positive for a target-serotype (0.8%), *S. Typhimurium* (culled), and in the second flock *S. Montevideo* was isolated. Additionally two parent breeding flocks for broiler production line entering the laying phase and originating from the same *Salmonella* - negative rearing flock were diagnosed positive of *S. Infantis* on the transport vehicle before entering the "production" - barn. During an epidemiological examination carried out by the official vet as well as extended official examinations of the flocks within the barn it could be proved, that the source of the positive results were the transporting boxes that had been used for the transport of a positive broiler flock and had not been cleaned and disinfected sufficiently. None of these flocks has been tested positive of *Salmonella* spp. during their whole laying phase. The EU-target was achieved in 2011.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - flocks of laying hens

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Laying hens flocks

At the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to regulation 1168/2006.

Frequency of the sampling

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: No legal requirements, e.g. at day one of each flock

Laying hens: Rearing period

3 times at day one, week 8 to 12 and 2 weeks before the laying period starts

Laying hens: Production period

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks with two pairs of boot swabs; an official veterinarian is testing every flock once a year according to regulation 1168/2006.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

3 weeks before slaughter at farm with two pairs of boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: Not applicable. No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: according to the program of the cooperatives voluntary surface swabs (e.g. every eight weeks)

Type of specimen taken

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Laying hens: Production period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces or drag swabs

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: Voluntary e.g. surface swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

2 pair of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: Production period

Industry sampling: 2 pair of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pair of boot swabs per flock, 25 g of dust and 60 pooled faeces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

No legal requirements, e.g. surface swabs

Case definition

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. Salmonella spp. isolated from hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Laying hens: Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs or dust or detection of antimicrobials or bacterial growth inhibitory effect in feces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Salmonella spp. isolated from surface swabs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used**Laying hens: Day-old chicks**

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Production period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no testing

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Vaccination policy**Laying hens flocks**

The national program made vaccination against Salmonella Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place**Laying hens flocks**

Nil

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place****Laying hens flocks**

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

All actions according to EU- and national legislation

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases**Laying hens flocks**

No class A eggs or culling in case of association with a food borne outbreak
EU regulation 1237/2007 is in force

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2011, 2,843 laying hen flocks were in production and have been tested. *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* were detected in 34 flocks (1.2 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2011.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

C. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - broiler flocks

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy****Broiler flocks**

Earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling**Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks**

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm 2 pairs of boot swabs 10 % of the flocks by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Type of specimen taken**Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks**

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled faeces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: no testing

Vaccination policy

Broiler flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Broiler flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Broiler flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Competitive exclusion strategies takes place.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Competitive exclusion strategies takes place.

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Competitive exclusion strategies takes place. Logistic Slaughtering is permitted for Salmonella spp. positive flocks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No testing

Notification system in place

All positive findings in parent flocks had to be notified to the local authority and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2011, 3,500 broiler flocks were in production and have been tested. S. Enteritidis or S. Typhimurium was detected in 15 flocks (0.4 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2011.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. Salmonella spp. in turkey - meat production flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Meat production flocks

Earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: no sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No sampling

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used**Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks**

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: see day-old chicks

Vaccination policy**Meat production flocks**

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place**Meat production flocks**

Nil

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place****Meat production flocks**

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Notification not mandatory

Notification system in place

Notification not mandatory

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Low prevalence of *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* (< 1%) in meat production turkey flocks

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2011, 340 turkey meat production flocks existed in Austria. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was detected in 2 (0.6%) turkey flocks. The EU-targeted was achieved in 2011.

Table 16 Salmonella spp. in poultry breeding flocks (*Gallus gallus*), 2011

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Hadar</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Virchow</i>	<i>S. 1,4,[5],12:i:-</i>	<i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>S. Schwarzengrund</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified	
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	14	QGV	Objective sampling	Official and industry sampling		ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock		14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	24	QGV	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling		ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock		24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), grandparent breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0		Census sampling	Official and industry sampling			Yes														
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), elite breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0		Census sampling	Official and industry sampling			Yes														
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	47	QGV	Objective sampling	Official and industry sampling		ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock		47	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	103	QGV	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling		ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock	*	103	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), grandparent breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0		Census sampling	Official and industry sampling			Yes														
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), elite breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0		Census sampling	Official and industry sampling			Yes														

* Two parent breeding flocks for broiler production line entering the laying phase and originating from the same Salmonella - negative rearing flock were diagnosed positive of *S. Infantis* on the transport vehicle before entering the "production" - barn. During an epidemiological examination carried out by the official vet as well as extended official examinations of the flocks within the barn it could be proved, that the source of the positive results were the transporting boxes that had been used for the transport of a positive broiler flock and had not been cleaned and disinfected sufficiently. None of the flocks has been tested positive of *Salmonella* spp. during their whole laying phase.

Table 17 Salmonella spp. in other commercial poultry, 2011

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium	<i>S.</i> Agona	<i>S.</i> Bovismorbificans	<i>S.</i> Coeln	<i>S.</i> Cubana	<i>S.</i> Hadar	<i>S.</i> Illib 6.1.i.i:z53	<i>S.</i> Illib 38.r:z	<i>S.</i> Indiana	<i>S.</i> Infantis	<i>S.</i> Kottbus	<i>S.</i> Llandoff	<i>S.</i> London	<i>S.</i> Manhattan	<i>S.</i> Mbandaka	<i>S.</i> Montevideo	<i>S.</i> Muenchen	<i>S.</i> Oranienburg	<i>S.</i> Saintpaul	<i>S.</i> Sentenberg	<i>S.</i> Stanley	<i>S.</i> Tennessee	<i>S.</i> Thompson	<i>S.</i> Worthington	
Gallus gallus (fowl)																																					
Laying hens																																					
During rearing period, control and eradication programmes	422	QGV	Objective sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd	1)	422	6	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2843	QGV	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd		2843	66	31	3	16	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	0	0	3	1	0	0	1	0	1	
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2843	QGV	Census sampling	Industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		2603	31	13	0	6	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2843	QGV	Objective sampling	Official sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		1677	35	18	3	10	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2843	QGV	Suspect sampling	Official sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		41	13	12	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gallus gallus (fowl)																																					
Broilers																																					
Before slaughter at farm, control and eradication programmes	3500	QGV	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd		3500	84	12	3	5	2	0	0	9	0	0	2	31	2	1	0	0	1	8	2	0	0	2	0	0	4	0	
Turkeys																																					
Breeding flocks, unspecified																																					
Adult, at farm, control and eradication programmes	0	QGV	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	0		Yes																														
Turkeys																																					
Fattening flocks, unspecified																																					
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	340	QGV	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd	2)	340	20	2	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	8	0	4	0	0	0	

1) one flock positive for SE and ST; 2) 2 different serotypes detected in 2 flocks (*S.* Infantis and *S.* Saintpaul; *S.* Montevideo and *S.* Saintpaul)

4.1.5. Salmonella spp. in feedstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Official monitoring based on risk assessment, own check programme by the industry based on HACCP.

Frequency of the sampling

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Process control in feed mills

Other: See above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: See above

Type of specimen taken

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Feed material of cereal grain and oil seed or fruit origin

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Imported feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Imported feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Process control in feed mills

Not applicable (n. a.)

Compound feeding stuffs

Feed for poultry

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 76/371/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Definition of positive finding

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Process control in feed mills

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Compound feeding stuffs

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2002; sample weight: 25 g; all isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and are serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Imported feed material of plant animal

Other: as above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Process control in feed mills

Other: as above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: as above

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999, § 3) and BGBl. Nr. 93/2000 (Futtermittelverordnung 2000, as amended) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 243/2000 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2000).

EC: VO (EG) 183/2005 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and VO (EG) 882/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to salmonella monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings

Domestic feed material of plant origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Notification system in place

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis of the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts, traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed and palletizing feed/contaminated feed. In 2011, data from feedingstuffs (only feedingstuffs for food producing animals, exclusive pet feed) indicate that the prevalence of salmonella (< 1%) remains very low. Although in pet feed Salmonella was detected in 14% (9 out of 66) of analysed samples.

Additional information

Nil

Table 18 Salmonella spp. in feed material of animal origin, 2011

Feed	sampStage	sampUnit	sampOrig	Sample weight	totUnitsTested	totUnitsPositive
Feed material of land animal origin *** blood products	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	DE	25g	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin *** fish meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	DE	25g	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin *** fish meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0
Feed material of marine animal origin *** fish meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	DE	25g	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin *** fish meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	4	0
Feed material of marine animal origin *** fish oil	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin *** fish oil	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	DE	25g	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin *** fish oil	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 19 Salmonella spp. in compound feeding stuff, 2011

Feed	sampStage	sampUnit	Sampling weight	sampOrig	toUnitsTested	toUnitsPositive	S. Agona	S. Brandenburg	S. Idikan	S. Isangi	S. Senftenberg	S. Typhimurium	S. Typhimurium, monophasic
Compound feedingstuffs for cattle *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	4	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	11	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	4	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	DE	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	NL	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	36	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	DE	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	NL	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** pelleted	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** pelleted	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs *** final product *** pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	3	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	5	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	6	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	11	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers *** final product *** pelleted	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers *** final product *** pelleted	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers *** final product *** pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	5	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens *** final product	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	47	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	14	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	9	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	54	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	DE	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens *** final product *** pelleted	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens *** final product *** pelleted	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens *** final product *** pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	3	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - pigeons	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - pigeons	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	6	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	4	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	6	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	34	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) *** final product *** pelleted	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) *** final product *** pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	DE	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	9	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	8	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys *** final product *** pelleted	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys *** final product *** pelleted	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys *** final product *** pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	5	0							
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	4	0							
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0							
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Pet food *** dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	at feed mill	single (food/feed)	25g	AT	3	0							
Pet food *** dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	at processing plant	single (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0							
Pet food *** dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	at retail	single (food/feed)	25g	AT	39	7	1	1	1	1	2	1	
Pet food *** dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	at retail	single (food/feed)	25g	CH	8	1					1		
Pet food *** dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	at retail	single (food/feed)	25g	DE	14	1					1		
Premixtures *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0							
Premixtures *** final product *** non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	DE	1	0							

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 20 Salmonella spp. in other feed matter, 2011

Feed	sampStage	sampUnit	Sampling weight	sampOrig	totUnits Tested	totUnits Positive	Salmonella *** S. Agona	Salmonella *** S. Lexington	Salmonella *** S. Mbandaka	Salmonella *** S. Montevideo	Salmonella *** S. Senftenberg
Feed material of cereal grain origin *** barley derived	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0					
Feed material of cereal grain origin *** wheat derived	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** groundnut derived	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** linseed derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** linseed derived	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	5	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** linseed derived	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	8	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** other	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** other oil seeds derived	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	4	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** other oil seeds derived	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** palm kernel derived	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** rape seed derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** rape seed derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	DE	2	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** rape seed derived	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	8	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** rape seed derived	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	26	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** soya (bean) derived	at farm	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	2	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** soya (bean) derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	8	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** soya (bean) derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	BR	1	1					1
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** soya (bean) derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	DE	1	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** soya (bean) derived	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	13	4	2		1	1	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** soya (bean) derived	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	47	2	1	1			
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** sunflower seed derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	3	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** sunflower seed derived	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	5	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** sunflower seed derived	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	9	0					
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin *** sunflower seed derived	at retail	batch (food/feed)	25g	DE	2	0					
Other feed material *** legume seeds and similar products	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	25g	AT	1	0					

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

4.1.6. Salmonella serovars and phage type distribution

The methods of collecting, isolating and testing of the Salmonella isolates are described in the chapters above respectively for each animal species, foodstuffs and in humans. The serotype and phage type distributions can be used to investigate the sources of the Salmonella infections in humans. Findings of same serovars and phagetypes in human cases and in foodstuffs or animals may indicate that the food category or animal species in question serves as a source of human infections. However, as information of the potential source of infection is not available, conclusions have to be made with caution.

Table 21 Salmonella serovars in humans, food and animals, 2011

Serovars	Humans	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat	Cattle	Pigs	Gallus gallus, fowl laying hens	Gallus gallus fowl, broilers	Turkey
	N=									
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	2235	4	3	60	30	16	29	175	105	106
Number of isolates per serovar										
S. Enteritidis	1266			1				118	17	6
S. Typhimurium	302	2	1			3	9	8	4	
monophasic S. Group B - 1,4,5,12 : i : -	73		1							
S. Stanley	71				2					7
S. Infantis	69			41				3	31	4
S. Bovismorbificans	37	1						1	3	10
S. Braenderup	27									1
S. Mbandaka	25							5	1	
S. Saintpaul	23				12			1		47
S. Paratyphi B var. Java	21									
S. Thompson	20			1				1	5	
S. Coeln	18	1	1	6	4			5		
S. Newport	16				1					
S. Hadar	14			3	2				15	
S. Kentucky	14			1	4		2			1
S. Virchow	13				2					
S. Brandenburg	13									2
S. Agona	13							16	6	5
S. Corvallis	12									
S. Kottbus	11							1	4	2
S. Oranienburg	8							3		
S. Monschau	8									
S. Napoli	8									
S. Montevideo	8			3			1	1	5	3
S. Muenchen	7								2	

Serovars		Humans	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat	Cattle	Pigs	Gallus gallus, fowl laying hens	Gallus gallus fowl, broilers	Turkey
		N=	2235	4	3	60	30	16	29	175	105
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped											
Number of isolates per serovar											
	S. Heidelberg		5						1		
	S. Derby		5					7			
	S. Senftenberg		5							2	3
	S. Bredeney		5			2		4		2	1
	S. Dublin		1				10				
	S. Rissen		3					4	3		11
	other serotypes		114		4	1	3	2	8	8	3

Data source: NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2012 (primary isolates in the NRC, exclusive S. Typhi and S. Paratyphi)

Table 22 S. Enteritidis phage types in humans, food and animals, 2011

Phagetypes S. Enteritidis		Humans	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat	Cattle	Pigs	Gallus gallus (fowl) laying hens	Gallus gallus (fowl) broiler	Turkey	
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped		N=										
Number of isolates per type		1266	0	0	1	0	0	0	118	17	6	
8		510			1				36		4	
4		198							23	1		
21		161							3	9		
6		147							15	4		
14b		48							3			
1		36							4			
RDNC		23							2	2		
2		20										
U		14										
3		12										
13a		11									2	
6a		10										
1b		8										
12		7							1			
14c		6										
15a		6										
29		6										
5		6										
7		6							9	1		
6b		5										
11		4										
6c		3										
5a		3										
7A		3										
23		2							18			
25		2										
13		2										
19a		1										
21c		1										
1a		1										
35		1										
4b		1										
3a		1										
20 var		1										
19									4			

Data source: NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2012 (primary isolates in the NRC)

Table 23 S. Typhimurium definitive types in humans, food and animals, 2011

Lysotypes <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	N=	Humans	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat	Cattle	Pigs	Gallus gallus (fowl) laying hens	Gallus gallus (fowl) broiler	Turkey
		302	2	1	0	0	3	9	8	4	0
120		69		1			2	1		1	
RDNC		54							3		
104L		47	2								
193		26								1	
3		26						6	5		
U302		13								2	
1		13					1				
135		13									
8		6									
85		5									
2		4									
41		4									
U		3									
U277		3									
208		3									
29		3									
12		2									
46		2									
99		2									
7A		1									
U311		1						2			
104H		1									
66A		1									

Data source: NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2012 (primary isolates in the NRC)

4.1.7. Antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella* spp. isolates

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of certain microorganisms to survive or grow in the presence of a given concentration of antimicrobial agent that usually would kill or inhibit the microorganism species in question. Antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* strains may be transferred from animals or foodstuffs to humans.

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The overall resistance-rates against antibiotics remained stable over the past years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The resistance rates remained stable. High level resistances against ciprofloxacin and third generation cephalosporins (cefotaxime) were still extremely rare in comparison to rates reported within the EU.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRL-S Report and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

B. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in animals and food

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method.

Salmonella isolates from the control programmes in laying hens, broilers and turkeys although were subjected to MIC-testing; all unique strains isolated from one epidemiological unit in the course of the control programmes.

Type of specimen taken

Monitoring samples; for animals and food see chapters *Salmonella* spp. in animal species and *Salmonella* spp. in food.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

For animals and food see chapters *Salmonella* spp. in animal species and *Salmonella* spp. in food.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method.

All unique strains isolated in the course of the control programm (identical strains from one epidemiological unit only once) were subjected to microdilution susceptibility testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter salmonellosis in humans; for the MIC testing CLSI standards are used, applying EU-RL (European Reference Laboratory) cut-off values.

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National Reference Centre for Salmonella, AGES Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All Salmonella isolates were susceptibility tested (disc diffusion) according to CLSI. Isolates obtained in course of the control programs were tested according CD Nr. 2007/407/EC. See corresponding tables! Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole.

Control program/mechanisms

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 24 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* spp., 2011**Test method used**

Disc diffusion	x
E-test	
Agar dilution	
Broth dilution	x

Standards used for testing

EUCAST	x
CLSI	x
EN ISO 20776-1	x

The methods are used for investigation of isolates from

Feedingstuff	
Animals	x
Food	x
Humans	x

<i>Salmonella</i>	Dilution method		Diffusion method		
	Standard for cut-off	Resistant > concentration (µg/ml)	Standard for breakpoint	Resistant ≤ zone diameter (mm)	
Tetracyclines					
	Tetracycline	EU-RL	8	CLSI	11
Amphenicols					
	Chloramphenicol	EU-RL	16	CLSI	16
	Floramphenicol	EU-RL	16		
Penicillins					
	Ampicillin	EU-RL	4	CLSI	13
Cephalosporins					
	Cefotaxim	EU-RL	0.5	CLSI	17
	Ceftazidime	EU-RL	2		
Fluoroquinolones					
	Ciprofloxacin	EU-RL	0.06	CLSI	18
Sulfonamides					
	Sulfamethoxazol	EU-RL	256	CLSI	12
Aminoglycosides					
	Streptomycin	EU-RL	32	CLSI	11
	Gentamicin	EU-RL	2	CLSI	13
	Kanamycin		4	CLSI	13
Quinolones					
	Nalidixic acid	EU-RL	16	CLSI	13
Polymyxine					
	Colistin	EU-RL	2		
Trimethoprim					
		EU-RL	2	CLSI	14

EU-RL = European Reference Laboratory

Table 25 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in humans, animals and food (diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2011

	S. Enteritidis																																			
	Humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			bovine meat			pig meat			laying hens			broiler			turkeys			cattle			pigs								
Isolates out of a monitoring																																				
Number of isolates available in the	1226			1			0			0			0			118			17			6			0			0								
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n			
Tetracyclines																																				
Tetracycline	1226	2,4	30	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	6	1	6	0	0												
Amphenicols																																				
Chloramphenicol	1226	0,1	1	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	0	0	6	0	0												
Penicillins																																				
Ampicillin	1226	3,5	43	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	35	6	6	0	0												
Cephalosporins																																				
Cefotaxim	1226	0,2	2	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	12	2	6	0	0												
Fluoroquinolones																																				
Ciprofloxacin	1226	0,0		1	0	0										118	0	0	17	0	0	6	0	0												
Sulfonamides																																				
Sulfamethoxazol	1226	0,3	4	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	6	1	6	0	0												
Aminoglycosides																																				
Streptomycin	1226	0,4	5	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	0	0	6	0	0												
Gentamicin	1226	0,0	0	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	0	0	6	0	0												
Kanamycin	1226	0,0	0	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	0	0	6	0	0												
Quinolones																																				
Nalidixic acid	1226	8,2	100	1	0	0										118	3,4	4	17	12	2	6	0	0												
Trimethoprim	1226	0,2	2	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	6	1	6	0	0												
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	1226	86,7	1062	1	100	1										118	96,6	114	17	64,7	11	6	100	6												
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	1226	12,2	150	1	0	0										118	3,4	4	17	5,9	1	6	0	0												
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1226	0,7	9	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	23,5	4	6	0	0												
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1226	0,2	3	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	0	0	6	0	0												
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1226	0	0	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	5,9	1	6	0	0												
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	1226	0,2	2	1	0	0										118	0	0	17	0	0	6	0	0												

Table 26 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2011

	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>																																
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)																																	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	302			0			0			2			1			8			4			0			3			9					
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																																	
Tetracycline	302	48,3	146							2	0	0	1	100	1	8	0	0	4	50	2							3	66,7	2	9	33,3	3
Amphenicols																																	
Chloramphenicol	302	22,5	68							2	0	0	1	0	0	8	0	0	4	0	0							3	66,7	2	9	11,1	1
Penicillins																																	
Ampicillin	302	46	139							2	0	0	1	100	1	8	0	0	4	50	2							3	66,7	2	9	11,1	1
Cephalosporins																																	
Cefotaxim	302	1,3	4							2	0	0	1	0	0	8	0	0	4	0	0							3	0	0	9	0	0
Fluoroquinolones																																	
Ciprofloxacin	302	0,0	0							2	0	0	1	0	0	8	0	0	4	0	0							3	0	0	9	0	0
Sulfonamides																																	
Sulfamethoxazol	302	49	148							2	100	2	1	100	1	8	25	2	4	50	2							3	66,7	2	9	11,1	1
Aminoglycosides																																	
Streptomycin	302	42,4	128							2	100	2	1	100	1	8	25	2	4	50	2							3	66,7	2	9	11,1	1
Gentamicin	302	0,3	1							2	0	0	1	0	0	8	25	2	4	0	0							3	0	0	9	0	0
Kanamycin	302	0	0							2	0	0	1	100	1	8	12,5	1	4	25	1							3	0	0	9	0	0
Quinolones																																	
Nalidixic acid	302	4,6	14							2	0	0	1	0	0	8	0	0	4	0	0							3	0	0	9	0	0
Trimethoprim	302	9,3	28							2	0	0	1	100	1	8	0	0	4	25	1							3	66,7	2	9	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates*	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	302	43,7	132							2	0	0	1	0	0	8	75	6	4	50	2							3	33,3	1	9	66,7	6
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	302	6,6	20							2	0	0	1	0	0	8	0	0	4	0	0							3	0	0	9	22,2	2
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	302	2,3	7							2	100	2	1	0	0	8	0	0	4	0	0							3	0	0	9	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	302	3,6	11							2	0	0	1	0	0	8	12,5	1	4	0	0							3	0	0	9	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	302	21,2	64							2	0	0	1	0	0	8	12,5	1	4	25	1							3	0	0	9	0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	302	22,5	68							2	0	0	1	100	1	8	0	0	4	25	1							3	66,7	2	9	11,1	1

Table 27 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* monophasic strain, 2011

	monophasic <i>S. Group B</i> (1,4,5,12 : i : -)																																
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)																																	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	70												1																				
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																																	
Tetracycline	70	97,1	68										1	100	1																		
Amphenicols																																	
Chloramphenicol	70	8,6	6										1	0	0																		
Penicillins																																	
Ampicillin	70	94,3	66										1	100	1																		
Cephalosporins																																	
Cefotaxim	70	0	0										1	0	0																		
Fluoroquinolones																																	
Ciprofloxacin	70	0,0	0										1	0	0																		
Sulfonamides																																	
Sulfamethoxazol	70	94,3	66										1	100	1																		
Aminoglycosides																																	
Streptomycin	70	94,3	66										1	0	0																		
Gentamicin	70	4,3	3										1	100	1																		
Kanamycin	70	4,3	3										1	0	0																		
Quinolones																																	
Nalidixic acid	70	1,4	1										1	0	0																		
Trimethoprim	70	5,7	4										1	0	0																		
Number of multiresistant isolates*	N	%	n										N	%	n																		
fully sensitive	70	1,4	1										1	0	0																		
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	70	2,9	2										1	0	0																		
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	70	1,4	1										1	0	0																		
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	70	2,9	2										1	0	0																		
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	70	81,4	57										1	100	1																		
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	70	10,0	7										1	0	0																		

Table 28 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis, Typhimurium and monophasic S. group B in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2011

	other serotypes than S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium and monophasic S. Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -)																																
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)																																	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	597			59			30			2			1			49			84			100			13			20					
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Tetracyclines																																	
Tetracycline	597	17,1	102	59	74,6	44	30	50	15	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	14,3	7	84	61,9	52	100	35	35	13	0	0	20	35	7			
Amphenicols																																	
Chloramphenicol	597	2	12	59	1,7	1	30	13,3	4	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	0	0	84	0	0	100	5	5	13	0	0	20	0	0			
Penicillins																																	
Ampicillin	597	9,9	59	59	5,1	3	30	46,7	14	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	4,1	2	84	22,6	19	100	29	29	13	0	0	20	45	9			
Cephalosporins																																	
Cefotaxim	597	1,2	7	59	0	0	30	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	0	0	84	0	0	100	0	0	13	0	0	20	45	9			
Fluoroquinolones																																	
Ciprofloxacin	597	2,3	14	59	1,7	1	30	13,3	4	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	0	0	84	0	0	100	1	1	13	0	0	20	0	0			
Sulfonamides																																	
Sulfamethoxazol	597	13,1	78	59	69,5	41	30	46,7	14	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	10,2	5	84	42,9	36	100	36	36	13	0	0	20	45	9			
Aminoglycosides																																	
Streptomycin	597	15,4	92	59	71,2	42	30	46,7	14	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	10,2	5	84	60,7	51	100	32	32	13	46,2	6	20	50	10			
Gentamicin	597	2,8	17	59	1,7	1	30	16,7	5	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	2	1	84	0	0	100	1	1	13	0	0	20	10	2			
Kanamycin	597	1,8	11	59	0	0	30	3,3	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	2	1	84	0	0	100	3	3	13	0	0	20	0	0			
Quinolones																																	
Nalidixic acid	597	28,6	171	59	76,3	45	30	66,7	20	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	8,2	4	84	59,5	50	100	49	49	13	0	0	20	40	8			
Trimethoprim	597	4,4	26	59	0	0	30	70	21	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	2	1	84	6	5	100	8	8	13	0	0	20	10	2			
Number of multiresistant isolates*	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	597	62,6	374	59	23,7	14	30	20	6	2	100	2	1	100	1	49	79,6	39	84	32,1	27	100	27	27	13	53,8	7	20	10	2			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	597	17,8	106	59	1,7	1	30	20	6	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	10,2	5	84	4,8	4	100	29	29	13	46,2	6	20	5	1			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	597	2,3	14	59	0	0	30	3,3	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	0	0	84	2,4	2	100	7	7	13	0	0	20	15	3			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	597	4,7	28	59	5,1	3	30	6,7	2	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	2	1	84	4,8	4	100	12	12	13	0	0	20	50	10			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	597	7	42	59	66,1	39	30	6,7	2	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	6,1	3	84	50,0	42	100	11	11	13	0	0	20	5	1			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	597	5,5	33	59	3,4	2	30	43,3	13	2	0	0	1	0	0	49	2	1	84	6	5	100	14	14	13	0	0	20	15	3			

Table 29 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella serotypes derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2011

	Gallus gallus laying hens, control program											
	S. Enteritidis			S. Typhimurium			S. Agona			S. other than Enteritidis, Typhimurium and Agona		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	38			3			23			22		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB												
Gentamicin	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	4,5	1
Kanamycin	38	2,6	1	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	4,5	1
Streptomycin	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	4,5	1
Cephalosporine												
Cefotaxim	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	0	0
Ceftazidime	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	0	0
Folsäureinhibitoren												
Sulfamethoxazol	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	9,1	2
Trimethoprim	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	4,5	1
Penicilline												
Ampicillin	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	9,1	2
Phenicole												
Chloramphenicol	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	0	0
Florfenicol	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	0	0
Polymyxine												
Colistine	38	34,2	13	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	0	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin												
Ciprofloxacin	38	7,9	3	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	9,1	2
Nalidixinsäure	38	7,9	3	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	4,5	1
Tetracycline												
Tetracycline	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	18,2	4
Number of multiresistant isolates												
fully sensitive	38	92,1	35	3	100	3	23	100	23	22	72,7	16
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	38	7,9	3	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	18,2	4
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	4,5	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	38	0	0	3	0	0	23	0	0	22	4,5	1

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 30 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella serotypes derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2011

		Gallus gallus broiler, control program											
		S. Enteritidis			S. Typhimurium			S. Infantis			S. other than Enteritidis, Typhimurium and Infantis		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		15			3			32			40		
Antimicrobials:		N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB													
	Gentamicin	15	0	0	3	0	0	32	0	0	40	0	0
	Kanamycin	15	0	0	3	33,3	1	32	0	0	40	0	0
	Streptomycin	15	0	0	3	33,3	1	32	28,1	9	40	27,5	11
Cephalosporine													
	Cefotaxim	15	13,3	2	3	0	0	32	0	0	40	0	0
	Ceftazidime	15	13,3	2	3	0	0	32	0	0	40	0	0
Folsäureinhibitoren													
	Sulfamethoxazol	15	6,7	1	3	33,3	1	32	100	32	40	5	2
	Trimethoprim	15	6,7	1	3	33,3	1	32	0	0	40	5	2
Penicilline													
	Ampicillin	15	26,7	4	3	33,3	1	32	0	0	40	30	12
Phenicole													
	Chloramphenicol	15	0	0	3	0	0	32	0	0	40	0	0
	Florfenicol	15	0	0	3	0	0	32	0	0	40	0	0
Polymyxine													
	Colistine	15	26,7	4	3	0	0	32	0	0	40	0	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin													
	Ciprofloxacin	15	0	0	3	0	0	32	100	32	40	25	10
	Nalidixinsäure	15	0	0	3	0	0	32	100	32	40	25	10
Tetracycline													
	Tetracycline	15	6,7	1	3	33,3	1	32	100	32	40	30	12
Number of multiresistant isolates													
	fully sensitive	15	73,3	11	3	66,7	2	32	0	0	40	65	26
	resistant to 1 antimicrobial	15	6,7	1	3	0	0	32	0	0	40	7,5	3
	resistant to 2 antimicrobials	15	13,3	2	3	0	0	32	0	0	40	0	0
	resistant to 3 antimicrobials	15	0	0	3	0	0	32	71,9	23	40	0	0
	resistant to 4 antimicrobials	15	6,7	1	3	0	0	32	28,1	9	40	22,5	9
	resistant to >4 antimicrobials	15	0	0	3	33,3	1	32	0	0	40	5	2

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 31 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella serotypes derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2011

	turkey, control program								
	S. Enteritidis			S. Saintpaul			S. other than Enteritidis, Typhimurium (n = 0) and Saintpaul		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	2			8			12		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	2	0	0	8	0	0	12	0	0
Kanamycin	2	0	0	8	0	0	12	0	0
Streptomycin	2	0	0	8	50	4	12	8,3	1
Cephalosporine									
Cefotaxim	2	0	0	8	0	0	12	0	0
Ceftazidime	2	0	0	8	0	0	12	0	0
Folsäureinhibitoren									
Sulfamethoxazol	2	0	0	8	50	4	12	33,3	4
Trimethoprim	2	0	0	8	50	4	12	8,3	1
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	2	0	0	8	50	4	12	0	0
Phenicole									
Chloramphenicol	2	0	0	8	0	0	12	0	0
Florfenicol	2	0	0	8	0	0	12	0	0
Polymyxine									
Colistine	2	0	0	8	0	0	12	0	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	2	0	0	8	87,5	7	12	66,7	8
Nalidixinsäure	2	0	0	8	87,5	7	12	58,3	7
Tetracycline									
Tetracycline	2	0	0	8	62,5	5	12	33,3	4
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	2	100	2	8	0	0	12	33,3	4
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	2	0	0	8	37,5	3	12	33,3	4
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	2	0	0	8	12,5	1	12	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	2	0	0	8	0	0	12	16,7	2
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	2	0	0	8	0	0	12	16,7	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	2	0	0	8	50	4	12	0	0

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 32 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2011

		<i>S. Enteritidis</i> laying hens, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		38																				
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:		= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
		n																				
	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	38	0					22	14	2													
Kanamycin	38	2,6									37	1										
Streptomycin	38	0								3	33	2										
Cephalosporine																						
Cefotaxim	38	0			17	21																
Ceftazidime	38	0					33	5														
Folsäureinhibitoren																						
Sulfamethoxazol	38	0										1	6	29	2							
Trimethoprim	38	0						38														
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	38	0							8	30												
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	38	0								1	30	7										
Florfenicol	38	0								2	36											
Polymyxine																						
Colistine	38	34,2								25	12	1										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	38	7,9				2	1															
Nalidixinsäure	38	7,9		8	27						35					3						
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	38	0							6	32												

Table 33 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2011

		<i>S. Typhimurium</i> laying hens, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		3																				
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:		=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
		n																				
	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																						
	Gentamicin	3	0	0			1	2														
	Kanamycin	3	0	0							3											
	Streptomycin	3	0	0							1	2										
Cephalosporine																						
	Cefotaxim	3	0	0	3																	
	Ceftazidime	3	0	0		3																
Folsäureinhibitoren																						
	Sulfamethoxazol	3	0	0										1	2							
	Trimethoprim	3	0	0				3														
Penicilline																						
	Ampicillin	3	0	0					1	2												
Phenicole																						
	Chloramphenicol	3	0	0							2	1										
	Florfenicol	3	0	0							2	1										
Polymyxine																						
	Colistine	3	0	0						3												
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
	Ciprofloxacin	3	0	0	1	2																
	Nalidixinsäure	3	0	0							3											
Tetracycline																						
	Tetracyclin	3	0	0						3												

Table 34 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2011

		<i>S. Agona</i> layers, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	23		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:			=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	23	0	0					3	19	1												
Kanamycin	23	0	0									23										
Streptomycin	23	0	0										15	8								
Cephalosporine																						
Cefotaxim	23	0	0				22	1														
Ceftazidime	23	0	0						23													
Folsäureinhibitoren																						
Sulfamethoxazol	23	0	0													23						
Trimethoprim	23	0	0						23													
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	23	0	0							17	6											
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	23	0	0									1	22									
Florfenicol	23	0	0									21	2									
Polymyxine																						
Colistine	23	0	0								23											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	23	0	0		15	8																
Nalidixinsäure	23	0	0									22	1									
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	23	0	0								23											

Table 35 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis, Typhimurium and Agona derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2011

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than Enteritidis, Typhimurium and Agona laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		22		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	22	4,5	1						6	13	2				1								
Kanamycin	22	4,5	1										21			1							
Streptomycin	22	4,5	1									1	9	10	1		1						
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	22	0	0				8	13		1													
Ceftazidime	22	0	0						9	11	2												
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	22	9,1	2												1	3	15	1					2
Trimethoprim	22	4,5	1							20	1						1						
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	22	9,1	2							2	12	6											2
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	22	0	0									1	10	10	1								
Florfenicol	22	0	0									2	17	2	1								
Polymyxine																							
Colistine	22	0	0									22											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	22	9,1	2	2	12	6			1		1												
Nalidixinsäure	22	4,5	1										20	1					1				
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	22	18,2	4								6	11	1				1	3					

Table 36 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2011

		<i>S. Enteritidis</i> broiler, control program																							
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																							
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		15																							
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																							
Antimicrobials:				= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048		
		N	%R	n																					
Aminoglykosid AB																									
	Gentamicin	15	0	0					7	8															
	Kanamycin	15	0	0									15												
	Streptomycin	15	0	0								1	14												
Cephalosporine																									
	Cefotaxim	15	13,3	2			10	3						2											
	Ceftazidime	15	13,3	2					11	2					2										
Folsäureinhibitoren																									
	Sulfamethoxazol	15	6,7	1											2	1	11							1	
	Trimethoprim	15	6,7	1						14							1								
Penicilline																									
	Ampicillin	15	26,7	4							5	6					4								
Phenicole																									
	Chloramphenicol	15	0	0								2	13												
	Florfenicol	15	0	0								2	13												
Polymyxine																									
	Colistine	15	26,7	4								11	4												
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																									
	Ciprofloxacin	15	0	0			7	8																	
	Nalidixinsäure	15	0	0									15												
Tetracycline																									
	Tetracyclin	15	6,7	1							2	12												1	

Table 37 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2011

		<i>S. Typhimurium</i> broiler, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	3		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:			=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	3	0	3																			
Kanamycin	3	33,3	2																			
Streptomycin	3	33,3	2																			
Cephalosporine																						
Cefotaxim	3	0	2 1																			
Ceftazidime	3	0	3																			
Folsäureinhibitoren																						
Sulfamethoxazol	3	33,3	2																			
Trimethoprim	3	33,3	2																			
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	3	33,3	1 1																			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	3	0	3																			
Florfenicol	3	0	3																			
Polymyxine																						
Colistine	3	0	3																			
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	3	0	3																			
Nalidixinsäure	3	0	3																			
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	3	33,3	2 1																			

Table 38 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2011

		<i>S. Infantis</i> broile, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	32		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:			= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	32	0	0					21	11													
Kanamycin	32	0	0								32											
Streptomycin	32	28,1	9												23	8	1					
Cephalosporine																						
Cefotaxim	32	0	0				13	16	3													
Ceftazidime	32	0	0					2	19	9	2											
Folsäureinhibitoren																						
Sulfamethoxazol	32	100	32																			32
Trimethoprim	32	0	0						32													
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	32	0	0							4	18	10										
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	32	0	0									10	19	3								
Florfenicol	32	0	0									12	18	2								
Polymyxine																						
Colistine	32	0	0								32											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	32	100	32					5	18	9												
Nalidixinsäure	32	100	32														32					
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	32	100	32													5	27					

Table 39 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than S. Enteritidis, S. Typhimurium and S. Infantis derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2011

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than Enteritidis, Typhimurium and Infantis broiler, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		40		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	40	0	0					7	31	2												
	Kanamycin	40	0	0								40											
	Streptomycin	40	27,5	11										19	10		7	2	2				
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	40	0	0			14	23	3														
	Ceftazidime	40	0	0					18	21	1												
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	40	5	2											3	10	24	1					2
	Trimethoprim	40	5	2						38							2						
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	40	30	12							18	8	2				12						
Phenicole																							
	Chloramphenicol	40	0	0								1	23	15	1								
	Florfenicol	40	0	0								1	32	6	1								
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	40	0	0								40											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	40	25	10	1	15	13	1	10														
	Nalidixinsäure	40	25	10									26	4			10						
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	40	30	12							4	23	1			2	9	1					

Table 40 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2011

		<i>S. Enteritidis</i> turkey, control program																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	2	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	2	0	0						2														
Kanamycin	2	0	0										2										
Streptomycin	2	0	0										2										
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	2	0	0				2																
Ceftazidime	2	0	0						1	1													
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	2	0	0													1	1						
Trimethoprim	2	0	0							2													
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	2	0	0									2											
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	2	0	0										1	1									
Florfenicol	2	0	0										2										
Polymyxine																							
Colistine	2	0	0									2											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	2	0	0		1	1																	
Nalidixinsäure	2	0	0										2										
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	2	0	0									2											

Table 41 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Saintpaul* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2011

		<i>S. Saintpaul</i> turkey control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	8		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:			=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	8	0	0					2	4	2												
Kanamycin	8	0	0									8										
Streptomycin	8	50	4										3	1		1		3				
Cephalosporine																						
Cefotaxim	8	0	0			6	2															
Ceftazidime	8	0	0					8														
Folsäureinhibitoren																						
Sulfamethoxazol	8	50	4												3	1					4	
Trimethoprim	8	50	4						4							4						
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	8	50	4							3	1					4						
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	8	0	0									3	5									
Florfenicol	8	0	0									8										
Polymyxine																						
Colistine	8	0	0								8											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	8	87,5	7		1			7														
Nalidixinsäure	8	87,5	7									1					7					
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	8	62,5	5							1	2					3	2					

Table 42 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than S. Enteritidis, S. Typhimurium (n = 0) and S. Saintpaul derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2011

		<i>Salmonella</i> other than <i>S. Enteritidis</i> , <i>S. Typhimurium</i> (n = 0) and <i>S. Saintpaul</i> turkey, control program																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	12	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Antimicrobials:				= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	12	0	0						3	9													
Kanamycin	12	0	0										12										
Streptomycin	12	8,3	1											9		2	1						
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	12	0	0				7	4	1														
Ceftazidime	12	0	0						6	5	1												
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	12	33,3	4													5	3						4
Trimethoprim	12	8,3	1							11							1						
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	12	0	0								8	4											
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	12	0	0										6	6									
Florfenicol	12	0	0										9	3									
Polymyxine																							
Colistine	12	0	0									12											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	12	66,7	8		3	1		1	4	3													
Nalidixinsäure	12	58,3	7										4		1				7				
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	12	33,3	4									8						1	3				

4.2. Campylobacteriosis

4.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

A. Thermotolerant Campylobacter general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases exceeded for the first time the number of notified salmonellosis cases in Austria. Since then, the gap between the number of human campylobacter cases and salmonella cases has been widening.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis – with the exception of 2003 – steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 6,077 cases in 2007. The number of Campylobacter cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases $n = 5,130$.

The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cow's raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Feedings stuff has no obvious relevance. Animals are diversly infected: broiler flocks around 50%, cattle approx. 25%. The actual source of infection is unknown in human cases, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

On January 1st, 2006, the Federal Zoonoses Act (128. Bundesgesetz: Zoonosengesetz, published on 18th November 2005) was implemented. The subject of this Act is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation to enable the collection of the information necessary in the EU. According to this Zoonoses Act, to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria, a Federal Commission for Zoonoses (Zoonoses Commission) has been founded to advise the Federal Minister. The first meeting took place on May 3rd, 2006. The tasks of this Zoonoses Commission are

- Securing of effective and continuous teamwork of special fields concerned
- Cooperation based on free exchange of general information and where necessary, of specific data
- Determination of measures in case of Austrian-wide food borne outbreaks (concerning several provinces by one outbreak)
- Issues the annually report on trends and sources of zoonoses in Austria
- Preparation of risk based, integrated monitoring and surveillance programmes

The Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of campylobacter prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of campylobacter in broiler and cattle was continued for the fifth year according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council and the Federal Zoonoses Act. The sampling was carried out from January to December 2010, and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years. In 2010, the monitoring program was suspended in pigs due to low relevance for human infections.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue to work for harmonization of monitoring programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.2.2. Campylobacteriosis in humans

A. Thermotolerant Campylobacter in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Campylobacter cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain
- Fever

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of Campylobacter spp. from stool or blood
- Differentiation of Campylobacter spp. should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Stool samples are plated on selective media and incubated in microaerobic atmosphere at 37 - 42 °C for a minimum of 36 hours (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 13). Campylobacter is confirmed by observing the typical colony morphology and characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope. For typing and differentiation of isolates to species level the production of catalase and oxidase, the reaction in hippurate and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis is performed. The differentiation to species-level is not performed in each laboratory.

Notification system in place

Notification of Campylobacteriosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases in Austria exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases for the first time. Since that year campylobacteriosis has remained the most frequently reported bacterial enteritis in humans in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2011 campylobacteriosis (n = 5,130) was the most frequently notified foodborne enteric disease. It seems that the main sources of infection are chicken meat and raw milk (Feierl G. 2007. Jahresbericht 2006 der Nationalen Referenzzentrale für Campylobacter. Mitteilungen der Sanitätsverwaltung 4/2007).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2011, campylobacteriosis remained the most frequently notified food borne disease in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria and the annual report of the National Reference Centre.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 43 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2011

	N	Cases			
		Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Campylobacteriosis	5130	61.04	3703	483	944
C. coli	96	1.14	69	10	17
C. fetus	1	0.01	0	1	0
C. hyointestinalis	4	0.05	4	0	0
C. jejuni	2128	25.32	1574	190	364
C. lanienae	1	0.01	1	0	0
C. lari	1	0.01	1	0	0
C. showae	1	0.01	1	0	0
C. sputorum	7	0.08	4	3	0
Campylobacter, not specified	451	5.37	277	37	137
unknown	2440	29.03	1772	242	426

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

Table 44 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age distribution, 2011

age groups	C. jejuni			C. coli			other species/not typed		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	27	20	7	0	0	0	43	30	13
1 to 4 years	173	106	67	6	2	4	262	155	107
15 to 24 years	468	255	213	18	10	8	562	303	259
25 to 44 years	576	297	279	28	12	16	789	395	394
45 to 64 years	348	217	131	26	12	14	538	305	233
5 to 14 years	260	159	101	4	2	2	316	187	129
65 years and older	276	147	129	14	6	8	396	207	189
All age groups	2128	1201	927	96	44	52	2906	1582	1324

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

Table 45 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution, 2011

	Campylobacter spp.	C. coli	C. jejuni	C. spp (other species)	C. spp (not specified)
Month	cases	cases	cases	cases	cases
January	289	4	154	1	130
February	233	7	98	0	128
March	283	2	27	2	252
April	271	1	25	0	245
May	447	0	77	0	370
June	678	5	268	1	404
July	630	19	387	5	219
August	623	8	345	3	267
September	535	7	191	2	335
October	473	7	129	0	337
November	384	21	236	1	126
December	284	15	191	0	78
Total	5130	96	2128	15	2891

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

4.2.3. Campylobacter in foodstuffs

A. Campylobacter, thermotolerant in food - all foodstuffs - official food

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2011 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2011“ (BMG-75500/0194-II/2010) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2011, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-dept information. In 2011, nine food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents

(Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0195-II/B/13/2010). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Samples are cultured either according to ISO 10272: 1995 or preenriched in Bolton bouillon at 42 °C for 48 hours and subsequently plated on CCDA- or modified CCDA agar at 42 °C for 48 hours microaerophilic. Campylobacter-like colonies were identified serologically, observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase. Not all isolates of Campylobacter spp. are differentiated.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

289 single samples of fresh broiler meat were tested and in 6.2% (= 18 samples) thermotolerant Campylobacter was found (2010: in 10%, 2009: in 26%). In 12 samples of pasteurised cows' milk, no sample was found positive as well as in 53 samples of raw cows' milk.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-001-11: Campylobacter spp. in meat from poultry, unspecified – meat preparation – intended to be eaten cooked - at retail - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January - December

Type of specimen taken

Meat from poultry, unspecified – meat preparation – intended to be eaten cooked

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Campylobacter spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up monitoring programs

Results of the investigation

141 samples tested, 67-times positive for Campylobacter spp.

Additional information

Nil

Table 46 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in poultry meat, 2011

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling details	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>Campylobacter coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	at processing plant		AT	single	25 g		5	5	1	4	0
	at retail		AT	single	25 g		5	4	1	3	0
	Unknown		AT	single	25 g		279	9	0	0	9
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Unknown		AT	single	25 g		230	1	0	0	1
Meat from geese - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail		DE	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail		AT	single	25 g		1	1	1	0	0
			XX	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	campaign A-001-11	AT	single	25 g		139	65	0	0	65
			DE	single	25 g		1	1	0	0	1
			IT	single	25 g		1	1	0	0	1
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail		AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail		AT	single	25 g		1	0	0	0	0

Table 47 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in food, 2011

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	CY	single	25 g		1	0
Crustaceans	at border control	XX	single	25 g		1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		14	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - chilled	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		19	0
		XX	single	25 g		1	0
		DE	single	25 g		1	0
	at slaughterhouse	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Meat from pig - fresh	at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0
	Unknown	AT	single	25 g		2	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - chilled	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten raw - chilled	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		5	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		94	0
		XX	single	25 g		1	0
		DE	single	25 g		3	0
	at slaughterhouse	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
		XX	single	25 g		1	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		11	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at farm	AT	single	25 g		6	0
		XX	single	25 g		2	0
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		5	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		10	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0
at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0	
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at farm	AT	single	25 g		9	0
		XX	single	25 g		1	0
	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		6	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		9	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	at cutting plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at retail	AT	single	25 g		4	0
Milk, sheep's - raw	at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0
Other food	at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0
	at retail	AT	single	25 g		13	0
		CN	single	25 g		1	0

4.2.4. Campylobacter in animals

A. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal - Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - faeces - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Since 2004 monitoring plans on the prevalence of selected zoonotic agents and their antimicrobial resistance have been performed annually. Based on the prevalence of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in cattle in 2009 the number of caecum samples was calculated (N = 622) to obtain 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. Caecal contents of slaughtered cattle of Austrian origin were sampled in slaughter houses where at least 80% of all cattle were slaughtered in 2010. The sampling had been stratified on the number of slaughtered animals by abattoirs all over Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the period of the study.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter:

The sampling was distributed by randomization over the whole year 2011.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter: Caecum containing a minimum of 50 to 100 grams of content.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration a part of the colon was ligated and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory some content of each colon was inoculated in selective bouillon suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

A bovine animal is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from its caecum.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Approximately 1 gram of content of the colon was enriched in Preston bouillon in microaerophilic atmosphere for 24 hours at 42 °C. Subsequently the preenrichment was plated on modified CCD agar (mCCDA) and incubated in microaerophilic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase.

For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates, hippurate reaction and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose pepton solution containing 10% glycerol or thioglycolate-broth at -70 °C.

For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli*.

Analysis was performed with Microsoft Excel 2010.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals must not be reported to authorities in Austria.

Results of the investigation

See respective tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 203 out of 622 (32.6%) caecum samples from slaughtered bovine animals thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were detected. Due to the 48% (165/342) prevalence of positive broiler slaughter batches for thermotolerant *Campylobacter*, there may be a higher risk for humans to get infected from poultry meat than from the consumption of beef or veal.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

B. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal – broiler - at slaughterhouse –official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2011 the monitoring on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* spp. was continued in broiler flocks. The period of sampling was randomized over the whole year. Sampling was performed in the 5 broiler slaughter facilities with slaughter batches consisting of >2000 animals in Austria in 2010.

Frequency of the sampling

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: according to the randomized sampling plan

Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Additionally a carcass from the same slaughter batch was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and plated on selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

At slaughter: A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from the pooled caecal content.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

At slaughter: The pooled samples were examined by direct inoculation on modified CCD agar (mCCDA) that was incubated in microaerophilic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase. For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates, hippurate reaction and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose peptone solution containing 10 % glycerol or thioglycolat-broth at -70 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Analysis was performed with Microsoft Excel 2010.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Different strategies are in discussion, e.g. a quick test for identification of *campylobacter* infected flocks at farm.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None.

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals must not be reported to authorities in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the course of this monitoring thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were detected in 165 out of 342 (48.3%) of the tested slaughter batches. Due to the fact that poultry is the animal species with the highest

prevalence of Campylobacter jejuni and coli, poultry meat seem to be the most risky food combined with mistakes in kitchen hygiene for humans acquiring an infection with C. jejuni/coli.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. Campylobacter spp. in animal - Pigs - at slaughterhouse – monitoring programme – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

No monitoring in 2011 due to the presumably low relevance of pigs for infections in humans (up to 99% of campylobacter in pigs are C. coli).

Table 48 Thermophilic *Campylobacter* spp. in animals, 2011

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	Campylobacter jejuni	Campylobacter coli
Broiler flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	IVET Graz	slaughter batch	342	165	109	56
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - calves (under 1 year)	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IVET Graz	animal	19	9	5	4
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - young cattle (1-2 years)	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IVET Graz	animal	162	68	56	12
Cattle (bovine animals) - adult cattle over 2 years	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IVET Graz	animal	441	126	96	30

IVET Graz: AGES Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Graz

Cattle: one sampling plan for all age groups

4.2.5. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter* spp.

A. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

A sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four designated diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* for speciation analysis and antimicrobial resistance testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Stool specimens were plated on *Campylobacter* blood-free selective media at 37°C or 42°C for 48 hours under micro aerobic conditions, and organisms were identified as *Campylobacter* spp. by oxidase testing and cell morphology. Isolates were speciated by hippurate hydrolysis, indoxyl acetate hydrolysis, katalase production, and species-specific real-time PCR.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Again, a further increase in resistance to fluoroquinolones was observed, the actual prevalence of antimicrobial resistance to ciprofloxacin in *Campylobacter jejuni* is 62.9 % throughout Austria. Resistance to tetracycline decreased to 24.0 %, and resistance to macrolides was not present (0 %).

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The newly established sentinel surveillance system will be continued. The results are published annually in the NRL-C Report and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

B. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in broiler meat

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

Isolates from broiler meat isolated in the course of the national food surveillance programs that were sent to the national reference centre for *Campylobacter* were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility.

Type of specimen taken

Food surveillance programs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant *campylobacter* in food

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Testing of all isolates will be performed in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. All *campylobacter* isolates from poultry meat were tested.

Methods used for collecting data

All informations concerning the tested food and results of the antimicrobial testing were entered and analysed in a Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant *campylobacter* in broilers.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

MIC values have been entered in a Microsoft® Excel datasheet.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin.

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2010, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A project has been started to assess the appropriate method for collecting data on antimicrobial usage in animals. Results of this study are expected for 2012.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2011, 54 % (45 out of 84) *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler meat showed resistance to ciprofloxacin and 24 % to tetracycline; no resistance was found against erythromycin. In *C. coli* even higher resistance rates were observed (ciprofloxacin 55 %, tetracycline 53 %). Compared to 2010, in *Campylobacter* spp. from broiler meat the resistance rates against ciprofloxacin and tetracycline were lower.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

C. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in animals

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers and cattle.

Type of specimen taken

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers and cattle

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers and cattle

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Testing of all isolates will be performed in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. The randomized sampling plan was calculated to obtain approximately 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* isolates per animal species. If less than 170 isolates were obtained, all isolates were tested. If more than 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were isolated 170 were randomly chosen.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals, sampled slaughterhouses and results of the antimicrobial testing were entered and analysed in a Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

MIC values have been entered in a Microsoft® Excel datasheet.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for Campylobacter includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin.

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2010, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A project has been started to assess the appropriate method for collecting data on antimicrobial usage in animals. Results of this study are expected in 2012.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2011, *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler showed higher resistance rates for ciprofloxacin of 69% (49% in 2008 to 59% in 2009 and 56% in 2010). For tetracycline the resistance rates decreased in 2011 to 17% (2008: 26%; 2009: 30%; 2010: 25%); similar trends could also be seen in isolates from humans; all isolates were sensitive for erythromycin as in the last years.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

Table 49 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*, 2011

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory
Disc diffusion	1
E-test	
Agar dilution	
Broth dilution	

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from	
CLSI	Feedingstuff	
other	Animals	x
EN ISO 20776-1	Food	
	Humans	x

<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)	
			Resistant >	lowest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 1	0,125	16
Neomycin	EUCAST	> 1	0,125	8
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 2	0,5	32
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination				
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	CLSI	> 16	1	64
Quinolone und Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EFSA	> 1	0,06	32
Nalidixinsäure	EUCAST	> 16	2	256
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 4	0,25	128
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 8	0,5	64
Phenicol				
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2	64
Polymyxine				
Colistin	DANMAP	> 32	4	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EFSA	> 2	0,125	64

Table 50 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data, 2011

		<i>C. jejuni</i> human																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	393	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	393	0,5	2						235	144	12			1	1							
Neomycin	393	1,0	4						13	217	152	7				4						
Streptomycin	393	2,3	9								285	94	5	1	1	4	3					
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:3)	393	0	0									163	200	28	2							
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	393	65,4	257				47	75	13	1				6	135	52	44	20				
Nalidixinsäure	393	64,4	253										36	80	22	2	1	4	56	172	20	
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	393	0,3	1							33	121	171	64	3							1	
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	393	28,0	110								1	14	38	143	87	23	17	49	21			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	393	0	0										229	97	48	19						
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	393	0	0											231	140	21	1					
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	393	31,0	122					47	125	45	41	13			4	4	6	15	93			

Table 51 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler meat, quantitative data, 2011

		<i>C. jejuni</i> broiler meat																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
Antimicrobials:				<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
		N	%R	n																	
Aminoglykosid AB																					
	Gentamicin	84	0	0					43	39	2										
	Neomycin	84	0	0					2	40	38	4									
	Streptomycin	84	1,2	1							59	22	2				1				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																					
	Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	84	0	0								29	51	3	1						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																					
	Ciprofloxacin	84	53,6	45				3	21	15				2	20	16	5	2			
	Nalidixinsäure	84	50	42									7	24	11				2	37	3
Makrolide																					
	Erythromycin	84	0	0						1	26	38	18	1							
Penicilline																					
	Ampicillin	84	22,6	19								3	5	26	31	6	4	7	2		
Phenicol																					
	Chloramphenicol	84	0	0									46	22	14	2					
Polymyxine																					
	Colistin	84	0	0										58	20	6					
Tetracycline																					
	Tetracyclin	84	23,8	20					5	27	19	12	1				1	5	14		

Table 52 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2011

		<i>C. jejuni</i>																				
		<i>Gallus gallus</i>																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		116		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Antimicrobials:		N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
Aminoglykosid AB					n																	
Gentamicin	116	0	0							53	56	6	1									
Neomycin	116	0	0						6	56	45	9										
Streptomycin	116	0,9	1								79	35	1				1					
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:	116	0	0										56	52	8							
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	116	69	80					14	18	4					2	47	17	9	5			
Nalidixinsäure	116	60,3	70											18	22	6		1		20	42	7
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	116	0	0							13	41	44	18									
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	116	31,9	37								1	5	19	34	20	12	6	15	4			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	116	0	0											66	32	12	6					
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	116	0	0												78	31	7					
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	116	17,2	20					9	45	23	14	5					3		5	12		

Table 53 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in cattle, quantitative data, 2011

		<i>C. jejuni</i> cattle																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	170	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	170	0,6	1						90	74	5			1								
Neomycin	170	0,6	1						11	83	72	3			1							
Streptomycin	170	2,9	5								125	39	1	2		1	1	1				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:	170	0	0									94	70	5	1							
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	170	33,5	57					35	70	8			1	1	33	15	4	3				
Nalidixinsäure	170	32,4	55										26	64	22	3		1	15	36	3	
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	170	0,6	1							12	45	70	41	1		1						
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	170	12,9	22								4	2	24	77	41	4	5	8	5			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	170	0,6	1										115	44	8	2	1					
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	170	0	0											106	57	7						
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	170	13,5	23						33	73	31	5	5					3	6	14		

Table 54 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*, 2011

Test method used		Number of reporting laboratory
Disc diffusion		1
E-test		
Agar dilution		
Broth dilution	x	

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from
CLSI	Feedingstuff
other	Animals
EN ISO 20776-1	Food
	Humans

<i>Campylobacter coli</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested	
			concentration (µg/ml)	
			Resistant >	lowest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 2	0,125	16
Neomycin	EUCAST	> 2	0,125	8
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 4	0,5	32
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination				
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	CLSI	> 16	1	64
Quinolone und Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EFSA	> 1	0,06	32
Nalidixinsäure	EUCAST	> 32	2	256
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 16	0,25	128
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 16	0,5	64
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2	64
Polymyxine				
Colistin	DANMAP	> 32	4	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EFSA	> 2	0,125	64

Table 55 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans quantitative data, 2011

		<i>C. coli</i> human																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	36	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	36	0	0						5	26	5											
Neomycin	36	2,8	1							4	25	6				1						
Streptomycin	36	16,7	6								4	23	3			2	1	3				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:	36	0	0										7	23	4	2						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	36	69,4	25					7	3	1				7	11	5		2				
Nalidixinsäure	36	69,4	25											10	1				14	10	1	
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	36	8,3	3							5	11	5	9	2	1					1	2	
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	36	16,7	6											4	15	11	2		4			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	36	2,8	1										8	18	8	1	1					
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	36	0	0											32	3	1						
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	36	36,1	13						2	8	7	3	3		1		1	1	10			

Table 56 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler meat - quantitative data, 2011

		<i>C. coli</i> broiler meat																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:																					
	N	%R	n																		
				n																	
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	47	0	0					5	36	6											
Neomycin	47	2,1	1					6	35	4	1				1						
Streptomycin	47	29,8	14						8	22	3				4	6	4				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																					
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	47	0	0							3	8	28	6	2							
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	47	55,3	26				7	9	5		3	2	15	6							
Nalidixinsäure	47	55,3	26								3	11	7			2	14	9	1		
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	47	2,1	1						3	15	9	13	5		1				1		
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	47	10,6	5								1	2	6	12	21	2		3			
Phenicol																					
Chloramphenicol	47	0	0									14	20	12	1						
Polymyxine																					
Colistin	47	0	0										39	7	1						
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	47	53,2	25					4	9	6	1	2	1			2	3	19			

Table 57 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler slaughter batches - quantitative data, 2011

		<i>C. coli</i>		<i>Gallus gallus</i>																	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		48		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
Antimicrobials:																					
		N %R n		n																	
				<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin		48	0	0					8	33	6	1									
Neomycin		48	2,1	1						10	30	7				1					
Streptomycin		48	20,8	10							14	20	4			4	3	3			
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																					
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:		48	0,0	0								7	15	19	6	1					
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin		48	79,2	38				2	6	2			2	11	11	10	4				
Nalidixinsäure		48	79,2	38										6	4			1	24	13	
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin		48	6,3	3						6	11	6	12	10							3
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin		48	14,6	7								1		14	16	10	3		4		
Phenicol																					
Chloramphenicol		48	0	0									10	27	10	1					
Polymyxine																					
Colistin		48	0	0										43	4	1					
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin		48	62,5	30					1	12	2	3					2	2	26		

Table 58 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in cattle - quantitative data, 2011

		<i>C. coli</i> cattle																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	14	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
Aminoglykosid AB				n																	
Gentamicin	14	0	0						4	9	1										
Neomycin	14	7,1	1							4	7	2				1					
Streptomycin	14	78,6	11								1	2			1	5		5			
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																					
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	14	0,0	0										4	9	1						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	14	35,7	5					1	3	5					2	3					
Nalidixinsäure	14	35,7	5											3	5	1			2	2	1
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	14	7,1	1								2	2	6	2	1					1	
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	14	7,1	1											3	4	6		1			
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	14	0	0										1	5	7	1					
Polymyxine																					
Colistin	14	0	0											10	4						
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	14	64,3	9					1	1	1	1	1	1	2					7		

4.3. Listeriosis

4.3.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy. In 2009 a further increase had to be assessed, 46 cases what corresponds to an incidence of 0.6. Two cases were associated with pregnancy. In 2010, a reduction to 34 cases could be observed and also in 2011, n = 24 (incidence of 0.29). The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2-0.9). Lethality reduced in 2011 to 8% (2 cases) compared to 26% in 2009. This (usually) high rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease.

The number of listeriosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately.

Restrictions tightened to sell unpasteurised milk in remote areas (Alps).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

More widespread information for pregnant and immunocompromised persons should be provided.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.3.2. Listeriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Cases are reported to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Listeriosis of newborns defined as Stillbirth or at least one of the following five in the first month of life:
 - Granulomatosis infantiseptica
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Dyspnoea
 - Lesions on skin, mucosal membranes or conjunctivae
- Listeriosis in pregnancy defined as at least one of the following three:
 - Abortion, miscarriage, stillbirth or premature birth
 - Fever
 - Influenza-like symptoms
- Other form of listeriosis defined as at least one of the following four:
 - Fever
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Localised infections such as arthritis, endocarditis, and abscesses

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally sterile site
- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally non-sterile site in a foetus, stillborn, newborn or the mother at or within 24 hours of birth

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the laboratory criteria

or

- Any mother with a laboratory confirmed listeriosis infection in her foetus, stillborn or newborn

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are Gram stained. Specimen from normally sterile sites are inoculated in blood culture broth or thioglycollate broth and Columbia blood agar plates, vaginal swabs are plated only directly on Columbia blood and colistin-nalidixic acid (CNA) agar. *L. monocytogenes* is identified by catalase and Api Listeria test.

Stool samples were examined after cold enrichment in Fraser enrichment broth and streaked onto selective chromogenic agar plate and Columbia blood-agar. All isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping by PCR and PFGE and comparison.

Notification system in place

Notification of listeriosis according to the Federeal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

History of the disease in chapter general evaluation.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

History of the disease

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression.

Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH

Table 59 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2011

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Listeriosis	26	0.31
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	13	0.16
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>	4	0.05
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	5	0.06
<i>unknown</i>	4	0.05
deaths caused by listeriosis		
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	1	0.01
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>	1	0.01
Congenital cases	0	

Data source: EMS as of June 4, 2012

Table 60 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution, 2011

Age group	Listeriosis			L. monocytogenes 1,2a			L. monocytogenes 1,2b			L. monocytogenes 4b			L. monocytogenes unspecified		
	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	1	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	1	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
45 to 64 years	6	5	1	3	2	1	1	1	-	1	1	-	1	1	-
65 years and older	18	8	10	8	4	4	3	1	2	4	1	3	3	2	1
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	26	13	13	13	6	7	4	2	2	5	2	3	4	3	1

Data source: EMS as of June 4, 2012

4.3.3. Listeria spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2011 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2011“ (BMG-75500/0194-II/2010) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2011, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2011, nine food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0195-II/B/13/2010). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used at the production plant or at retail

Qualitative detection of *Listeria* spp. is performed according to ISO 11290: Part 1 (1996).

Quantification of *Listeria* spp. content in food is conducted either according to ISO 11290: Part 2 (1998) with following modifications: *Listeria monocytogenes* are confirmed on Ottaviani Agosti Agar, ALOA Agar, RapidLmono agar, using Gram stain, motility testing and catalase production or by the Api *Listeria* test or Vidas LMO II.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Listeria monocytogenes was not detected in samples of pasteurised cows' milk (0/56) nor in 74 samples of extended self life milk (campaign A-036-11). Within the 425 samples of raw cows' milk only 1 sample was qualitatively found positive for *L. monocytogenes* in 25g and quantitatively <100 cfu/g. Also in 47 of 815 ready-to-eat pig meat product samples (including fermented sausages) *L. monocytogenes* was found and in 38 out of 239 pig meat fresh samples *L. monocytogenes* was qualitatively found in 25g.

8.9 % of all samples from fishery products (16/180), including campaign (A-042-11) revealed a contamination with *L. monocytogenes* (1-time <100 cfu/g). 3 of 15 raw fish samples (20%) were positive for *L. monocytogenes*, 3- times *L. monocytogenes* was qualitatively found in 25g.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by the AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Pregnancy – infections transmitted via food (Schwangerschaft – Infektionen durch Nahrungsmittel,

http://www.ages.at/uploads/media/AGES_Folder_Schwangerschaft_Web.pdf). This folder was distributed to all gynaecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during

pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-022-11: Listeria in food – Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

46 samples tested for Listeria monocytogenes: qualitative method: 4 samples positive in 25 g, quantitative method: 2-times <10 cfu/g, 1-time 30 cfu/g, 1-time 80 cfu/g

Additional information

Samples were also tested for VTEC and Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-030-11: Listeria in food – Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - August

Type of specimen taken

Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

78 samples tested for Listeria monocytogenes: qualitative method: 5 samples positive in 25 g, quantitative method: 4-times <10 cfu/g, 1-time 1,150 cfu/g

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-036-11: Listeria in food – Milk, cows' – extended shelf life milks - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: July - September

Type of specimen taken

Milk, cows' – extended shelf life milk

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

74 samples tested for Listeria monocytogenes: qualitative method: 0-times positive for Listeria monocytogenes

Campaign A-042-11: Listeria in food – Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - October

Type of specimen taken

Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat – chilled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

34 samples tested for Listeria monocytogenes: qualitative method: 5 samples positive in 25 g, quantitative method: 5-times <10 cfu/g

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-049-11: Listeria in food – Fish – smoked - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: October - December

Type of specimen taken

Fish – smoked

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

36 samples tested for Listeria monocytogenes: qualitative method: 2 samples positive in 25 g,
quantitative method: 2-times <10 cfu/g

Table 61 *Listeria monocytogenes* in milk and milky products, 2011

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > 100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from cows' milk - curd	at retail	AT		8	0	8	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		27	0	24	0	26	0	0
		at retail	AT	11	0	11	0	8	0	0
		CY	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
		DE	3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
		IT	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
	XX	1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	at retail	AT		12	0	11	0	6	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		at retail	AT	9	0	9	0	6	0	0
		IE	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
		IT	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		XX	4	0	4	0	4	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		27	0	27	0	27	0	0
		at retail	AT	17	0	17	0	16	0	0
		DE	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		IT	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		123	0	119	0	105	0	0
		at retail	AT	83	0	83	0	65	0	0
		BE	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		CH	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		CY	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		DE	26	0	23	0	25	0	0	
		DK	2	0	2	0	1	0	0	
		ES	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		FR	10	0	10	0	9	0	0	
		GR	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		IT	8	0	8	0	8	0	0	
		SI	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		TR	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		XX	13	0	13	0	6	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		19	0	19	0	17	0	0
	at retail	AT		35	0	35	0	29	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		FR		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	IT		2	0	2	0	1	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
		DE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		at retail	AT	10	0	10	0	10	0	0
		DE	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		FR	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		PL	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from goats' milk	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT		14	0	14	0	14	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		17	0	16	0	13	0	0
	at retail	AT		15	0	15	0	13	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		DK		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		GR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
NL		1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	at retail	AT		7	1	7	1	7	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
		NL		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		12	0	12	0	11	0	0
	at retail	AT		10	0	9	0	10	0	0
		GR		5	0	5	0	3	0	0
		NL		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		7	0	7	0	3	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	5	0	0
	at retail	AT		4	0	3	0	4	0	0
		CY		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		GR		6	0	6	0	2	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		FR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	at processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		9	1	9	1	8	0	0
		DE		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		HU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		IT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		SK		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	at processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
		DE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		FR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	7	0	0
	at retail	AT		29	0	29	0	20	0	0
		PL		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		SI		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
SK		1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream	at catering	XX		30	0	30	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts - chilled	at processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at border control	IL		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		28	0	28	0	26	0	0
	at retail	AT		14	0	14	0	14	0	0
		DE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	at processing plant	AT		3	0	2	0	3	0	0
	at retail	AT		10	0	9	0	3	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at processing plant	AT		11	0	10	0	11	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk	at catering	XX		13	0	13	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - sour milk	at processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - extended shelf life milk	at retail	AT	campaign A-036-11	74	0	74	0	74	0	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		34	0	34	0	21	0	0
	at retail	AT		20	0	20	0	11	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at farm	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	at retail	AT		10	0	10	0	9	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	Unknown	XX		425	1	425	1	425	0	1
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at farm	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
	at retail	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw milk	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0

Table 62 *Listeria monocytogenes* in other foods, 2011

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Bakery products - cakes	at retail	AT		83	0	83	0	75	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Bakery products - pastry	at catering	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	at retail	AT		98	2	97	2	91	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		GR		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		IT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		JP		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		TW		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Chocolate	at retail	DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Confectionery products and pastes	at catering	XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans	at border control	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		NL		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
XX		2	1	2	1	1	0	0		
Fish - marinated	at retail	XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fish - raw	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
	at retail	ES		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		DK		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		GL		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		GR		2	1	2	1	0	0	0
		LK		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		NO		1	1	1	1	0	0	0
		PH		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		3	1	3	1	1	0	0
Fish - raw - chilled	at catering	XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	at retail	XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - smoked	at retail	AT	campaign A-049-11	36	2	36	2	36	0	0
	Unknown	XX		31	1	31	1	31	0	0
Fish - smoked - cold-smoked	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified	at catering	XX		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		19	0	19	0	17	0	0
	at retail	AT		37	2	37	2	32	0	0
		CA		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		CZ		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		DE		16	1	16	1	15	0	0
		DK		12	1	12	1	11	0	0
		GL		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		FR		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		LT		2	1	2	1	2	0	0
		NL		5	1	5	1	4	1	0
		NO		7	1	7	1	7	0	0
		PL		16	0	16	0	15	0	0
		SE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
TR		2	0	2	0	2	0	0		
TW		1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
XX		4	2	4	2	4	0	0		
Fishery products, unspecified - non-ready-to-eat - chilled	at catering	XX		5	0	5	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - non-ready-to-eat - frozen	at catering	XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled	at retail	AT	campaign A-042-11	34	5	34	5	34	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - seafood pate	at retail	XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fruits	at retail	AT		1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Infant formula	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at processing plant	AT		4	1	4	1	4	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		4	1	4	1	3	0	0
	Unknown	XX		47	3	47	3	47	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		21	3	21	3	12	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
	at slaughterhouse	AT		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh	at processing plant	AT		5	1	5	1	5	0	0
	at retail	AT		5	1	5	1	5	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation	at game handling es	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products	at processing plant	AT		3	1	3	1	3	0	0
	at retail	AT		10	0	10	0	9	0	0
		IT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Unknown	XX		235	38	235	38	235	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked - chilled	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT		1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked ham - sliced	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		6	2	6	2	6	0	1
	Unknown	XX		787	42	787	42	787	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - fermented sausages	at retail	AT		15	3	15	3	3	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - pâté	at catering	XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw ham	at retail	XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT		3	1	3	1	2	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at processing plant	AT		2	1	2	1	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		DE		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products	Unknown	XX		20	3	20	3	20	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat - sliced	at retail	AT		12	0	12	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked - chilled	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		97	16	97	16	71	0	0
		DE		3	2	3	2	2	0	0
		XX		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
	at slaughterhouse	AT		1	1	1	1	1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes > 100 cfu/g
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	at catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		8	0	8	0	6	0	0
	at retail	AT		55	2	55	2	37	0	0
		DE		8	0	8	0	7	0	0
		ES		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		FR		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		HU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT		5	0	5	0	4	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		45	1	45	1	41	0	0
	at retail	AT		71	6	71	6	56	0	0
		DE		3	0	3	0	1	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		PL		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		SI		4	0	4	0	2	0	0
XX		2	0	1	0	2	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at game handling es	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		20	2	20	2	18	0	0
	at retail	AT		69	7	69	7	57	1	0
		DE		9	0	9	0	8	0	0
		ES		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
		HU		5	1	5	1	4	0	0
IT			10	1	10	1	8	0	0	
SI		4	0	4	0	2	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Molluscan shellfish - cooked	Unknown	XX		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Mushrooms	at retail	DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		ES		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Other food	at retail	AT		30	1	30	1	13	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		GR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other food of non-animal origin	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		26	0	26	0	23	0	0
TH			1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	at retail	AT		41	0	41	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta/rice salad	at catering	XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods	at retail	AT	campaign A-022-11	46	4	46	4	46	2	0
		AT	campaign A-030-11	78	5	78	5	78	1	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - chilled	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		11	0	11	0	8	0	0
DE			4	0	4	0	1	0	0	
Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise	at retail	AT		5	0	5	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise	at catering	XX		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Vegetables	at retail	AT		2	0	1	0	2	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Vegetables - products	at retail	AT		2	0	1	0	2	0	0
Vegetables - products - cooked - chilled	at catering	XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0

4.4. Verotoxic Escherichia coli

4.4.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2011, an increase of VTEC-cases in Austria could be observed, up to 129 cases (88 cases in 2010). One reason for the increase was the O104-outbreak in Germany that led to a higher number of feces samples that were tested for VTEC. 10 cases of HUS were diagnosed, 6 of them caused by O157, the other cases were caused by other serotypes.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The prevalence of verotoxin producing E. coli isolated from cattle increased to 40 % and from sheep to 68 %, but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA, the sampling material (rectum-anal swabs) and improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques (see chapter Pathogenic Escherichia coli in animals). Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), O157 (5 x), O145 (2 x) and O103 (1 x) were isolated from cattle and O103 (1 x) from sheep.

The relevance of findings of VTEC in feces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines and sheep.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

An Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Orders. The sampling was carried out throughout 2011 and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, paediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.4.2. Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Cases are reported to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

STEC/VTEC diarrhoea

Any person with at least one of the following two symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain

HUS

Any person with acute renal failure and at least one of the following two:

- Microangiopathic haemolytic anaemia
- Thrombocytopenia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following three:

- Isolation of Shigatoxin/Verotoxin (STEC/VTEC) producing E. coli
- Detection of *vtx1* or *vtx2* gene(s) nucleic acid
- Detection of free shigatoxins.

Only for HUS the following can be used as laboratory criterion to confirm STEC/VTEC:

- E. coli serogroups specific antibody response

Isolation and additional characterisation by serotype, phage type, *eae* genes, and subtypes of *stx1/stx2* should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case of STEC-associated HUS

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria for HUS

Probable case of STEC/VTEC

• Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link or a laboratory confirmed case without clinical criteria

Confirmed case of STEC/VTEC

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

1. Detection of E. coli O157 (most prominent serotype in HUS cases):

- Bacteriology: Isolation of O157 colonies on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar (or CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey agar) after incubation for 24 hours at 37 °C (or 41°C). O157 is confirmed via the E. coli O157 Latex Test.

- Serology: This method is constantly used at the German HUS-"Konsiliarlabor"; anti-O157 antibodies of IgG and IgM types can be distinguished.

2. Detection of Verotoxin (VTEC)-producing strains (used at the National Reference Laboratory/Center for EHEC/VTEC/STEC): Stools are enriched overnight in a medium containing mitomycin C (EHEC Direct Medium, Heipha, Heidelberg, Germany). Enriched cultures are plated on selective agar (CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey, Enterohemolysin, and Sorbitol-MacConkey). After incubation for 18-24 hours at 37°C a representative mixture of the viable cells were subjected to PCR reactions analyzing *stx1*, *stx2*, *eae* and *Ehly* (Reischl et al. (2002), Journal of Clinical Microbiology, p. 2555-2565). Isolates are gained via colony picking and pathotyped with the same PCR scheme. Isolate identification is further confirmed by conventional biochemical tests (VITEK or Api 20E, bioMerieux, Marcy-l'Étoile, France).

All EHEC/STEC/VTEC isolates obtained in Austria are to be sent to the National Reference Laboratory for confirmation, subtyping and comparison. All Shiga toxin producing E. coli are serotyped with E. coli antisera (E. coli antisera, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark). Comparison of the isolates is done by Pulsed-Field-Gel-Electrophoresis and Ribotyping.

Notification system in place

Notification of VTEC according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance as a zoonotic disease

HUS is a rare complication of E. coli infection; however EHECs themselves are not rare, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, most of which are currently unknown. Although raw or undercooked meat and unpasteurised dairy products are likely candidates to transfer the bacterium to humans, the actual source of infection often remains unclear. The importance of hand hygiene after animal contact should be always considered.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH

Table 63 Verocytotoxigenic Escherichia coli infections in human - species/serotype distribution, 2011 (EMS)

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	unknown
HUS	10	0.12	7	2	1
- clinical cases					
- lab. confirmed cases	10	0,12	7	2	1
- caused by O157 (VT+)	6	0,07	4	1	1
- caused by other VTEC	3	0,04	2	1	0
- unknown serovar	1	0,01	1	0	0
E.coli infect. (except HUS)	104	1,24	71	17	16
- clinical cases					
- laboratory confirmed	104	1,24	71	17	16
- caused by O157 (VT+)	23	0,27	15	4	4
- caused by other VTEC	73	0,87	51	12	10
- unknown serovar	8	0,10	5	1	2
HUS status not known	15	0,18	8	1	6
- lab. confirmed cases	15	0,18	8	1	6
- caused by O157 (VT+)	1	0,01	1	0	0
- caused by other VTEC	11	0,13	5	0	6
- unknown serovar	3	0,04	2	1	0
VTEC gesamt	129	1.54	86	20	23

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

Table 64 Verocytotoxigenic Escherichia coli infections in human - age distribution, 2011

age groups	E. coli infection (except HUS)			HUS			HUS status not known		
	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F
< 1 year	12	7	5	1	-	1	3	1	2
1 to 4 years	46	26	20	5	3	2	7	4	3
5 to 14 years	14	7	7	2	1	1	1	1	-
15 to 24 years	6	4	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	8	5	3	2	-	2	3	1	2
45 to 64 years	10	6	4	-	-	-	1	-	1
65 years and older	8	3	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gesamtergebnis	104	58	46	10	4	6	15	7	8

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

4.4.3. Pathogenic Escherichia coli in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2011 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2011“ (BMG-75500/0194-II/2010) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2011, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2011, nine food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0195-II/B/13/2010). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

25 g of the sample is pre-enriched using modified tryptic soy broth containing novobiocin (mTSB + n) for 24h at 37 °C. Subsequently about 1 microliter is plated on trypton-bile-glucuronid (TBX) for 24h at 37 °C. 5 colonies per plate are identified as E. coli (indole positive, glucuronidase positive or using enterotube. E. coli are tested in a multiplex PCR for stx1 and stx2 (Brian et al, 1992. Polymerase chain reaction for diagnosis of enterohemorrhagic Escherichia coli infection and haemolytic-uremic syndrome. J Clin Microbiol 30, 1801-06).

The typing for virulence factors as the eae-gene and serotyping is carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-022-11: VTEC in food - Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

46 samples tested, VTEC: 1-time positive (Orough:HNM)

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp. and Listeria monocytogenes

Table 65 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in food, 2011 part 1

Food	Sampling details	Sampling stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	VTEC O105:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O17:H9 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O27:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H10 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive
Bakery products - cakes		at retail	AT	single	1 g		1	0							
Bakery products - pastry		at retail	AT	single	1 g		1	0							
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at processing plant	AT	single	1 g		1	0							
				25 g		1	0								
		at retail	AT	single	1 g		2	0							
				25 g		3	1						1		
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk		at retail	IT	single	25 g		1	0							
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		at processing plant	AT	single	1 g		4	0							
				25 g		1	0								
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
				1 g		1	0								
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		4	0							
				1 g		1	0								
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk		at processing plant	AT	single	1 g		1	0							
Cheeses made from goats' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at retail	AT	single	1 g		1	0							
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk		at processing plant	AT	single	1 g		1	0							
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk		at processing plant	AT	single	1 g		2	0							
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
				1 g		1	0								
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk		at retail	GR	single	25 g		1	0							
				1 g		1	0								
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at retail	AT	single	1 g		1	0							
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk		at retail	SK	single	25 g		1	0							
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
Fish - raw		at retail	XX	single	25 g		1	0							
Fruits		at retail	AT	single	25 g		16	0							
				ES	single	25 g		13	0						
Juice - fruit juice - pasteurised		at cutting plant	AT	single	25 g		17	0							
				AT	single	25 g		3	0						
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		4	0							
				AT	single	25 g		3	0						
				XX	single	25 g		1	0						
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	AT	single	25 g		8	0							
				DE	single	25 g		1	0						
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
				AT	single	25 g		5	0						
				DE	single	25 g		1	0						
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation		at game handling establishment	AT	single	25 g		2	0							
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		2	1							
				AT	single	25 g		9	2			1	1		
				IT	single	25 g		4	1			1			
Meat from other animal species or not specified		at retail	AT	single	25 g		7	1	1						
				DE	single	25 g		1	0						
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
				AT	single	25 g		3	0						
				DE	single	25 g		2	0						
Meat from sheep - fresh		at border control	AU	single	25 g		1	0							
Meat from sheep - meat preparation		at retail	AT	single	25 g		3	0							
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
				AT	single	25 g		36	0						
				DE	single	25 g		1	0						
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	1							

Table 66 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in food, 2011 part 2

Food	Sampling details	Sampling stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive	VTEC O105:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2	VTEC O172:H9 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O27:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2	VTEC ONT:H10 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products		at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		6	0							
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		at processing plant	DE	single	25 g		2	0							
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		6	0							
			SI	single	25 g		4	0							
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		at catering	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
		at game handling establishment	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		10	0							
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		54	0							
			IT	single	25 g		10	0							
			ES	single	25 g		4	0							
			DE	single	25 g		7	0							
	SI	single	25 g		4	0									
	HU	single	25 g		5	0									
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	AT	single	25 g		9	0							
Milk from other animal species or unspecified		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
			XX	single	25 g		1	0							
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
Milk, cows' - raw		at farm	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		5	0							
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		6	0							
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		at farm	AT	single	25 g		8	0							
		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		4	0							
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		7	0							
Milk, sheep's - raw		at retail	AT	single	25 g		2	0							
Mushrooms		at retail	XX	single	25 g		1	0							
			ES	single	25 g		1	0							
			DE	single	25 g		1	0							
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		at retail	AT	single	1 g		2	0							
					25 g		2	0							
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods	campaign A-022-11	at retail	AT	single	25 g		46	1							1
Ready-to-eat salads		at retail	AT	single	1 g		1	0							
Seeds, dried		at retail	AT	single	25 g		6	0							
			XX	single	25 g		4	0							
			DE	single	25 g		4	0							
Spices and herbs		at retail	AT	single	25 g		1	0							
			EG	single	25 g		1	0							
Vegetables		at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		3	0							
		at retail	AT	single	25 g		29	0							
			IT	single	25 g		6	0							
			XX	single	25 g		1	0							
			ES	single	25 g		32	0							
			DE	single	25 g		2	0							
			NL	single	25 g		8	0							
			PL	single	25 g		1	0							
		Unknown	AT	single	25 g		4	0							

4.4.4. Pathogenic Escherichia coli in animals

A. Verotoxigenic Escherichia coli in cattle (bovine animals)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

The monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in slaughtered cattle was continued. The sampling was stratified based on the number of processed animals per abattoir in Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the year 2011. Sampling was performed in the 31 abattoirs which processed more than 80 % of Austria's cattle in 2010.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter

The sampling was distributed randomly over the period of the study from January to December 2011.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter

A part of the intestine containing rectum and anus.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at slaughter

The sampling is performed by qualified veterinarians who carry out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration, a part of rectum and anus was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C, the sample had been sent to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz the same day, in a hobbox or polystyrene box along with cooling packs. In the laboratory, a swab from the rectum-anal mucosa was incubated in a broth.

Case definition

Animals at slaughter

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from its recto-anal mucosa.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at slaughter

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation.

At first the swab was pre-enriched using modified tryptic soy broth containing novobiocin (mTSB + n) for 5 hours at 37 °C on a shaker. Then 1 ml of each pre-enrichment was inoculated into mTSB + n containing mitomycin C for 18-20 hours at 37 °C on a shaker too. The process was followed by testing the enrichment for the occurrence of verotoxin in an enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA, Premier TM EHEC). Positive enrichments were plated on MacConkey (MAC) -, on cefixime tellurite sorbitol MAC (CTSMAC) - and on enterohemolysin agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. 2-4 colonies from each of the plates were subcultured on MAC as well as on CTSMAC. Afterwards the genomes of subcultured E. coli were investigated in a real time PCR for harboring the genes for Verotoxin 1, Verotoxin 2, Intimin and Enterohemolysin (Reischl U. et al. 2002: Real-Time Fluorescence PCR Assays for Detection and Characterization of Shiga Toxin, Intim and Enterohemolysin Genes from Shiga Toxin-Producing Escherichia coli. Journ of Clin Microb, 40, p 2555-2565).

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Center for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification system in place at this time.

Results of the investigation

See table.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from bovine remained high (40 %); we hypothesize that this is due to a high sensitivity of the ELISA, the sampling material (recto-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar. Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), O157 (5 x), O145 (2 x) and O103 (1 x) were isolated from cattle.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in feces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) in animal - Sheep

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in sheep at farm:

The monitoring in 2011 was directed towards sheep at farms. 116 sheep (out of 116 different farms) had to be tested, calculated on a population of sheep of 350,000 in Austria in 2011. The sampling had been stratified on the number and size of sheep holdings in Austrian provinces.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at farm:

The sampling was done after blood sampling in course of the Brucella melitensis control program.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at farm:

Recto-anal swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at farm:

The swab was sent in transport medium cooled down to 4 °C and the fleece in a separate plastic bag in a hobbcock or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory, the swab and fleece were inoculated into separate broths.

Case definition

Animals at farm

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from one of the samples tested.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at farm

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation, see chapter above.

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification

Results of the investigation

See table.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from sheep remained high but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA, the sampling material (recto-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar. Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), only O103 (1 x) was isolated from sheep.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in/on sheep seems to be low because sheep meat is consumed well-done.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 67 Verotoxin producing Escherichia coli in animals, 2011

animal species	sampling context	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin ELISA positive units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O103:H2 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O104:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O107:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O107:HNT - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O107:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O108:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O112ab:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O113:H4 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H4 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O117:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O128abc:H - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O128abc:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O128abc:HNT - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O128abc:HNT - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O13:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O145:H - eae positive vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O145:H12 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H12 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:HNT - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O157:H - eae positive vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O157:H - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O157:H7 - eae positive vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O160:HNT - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive			
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	6	4	3	0														1																	
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - young cattle (1-2 years)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	40	28	13	2						1																							2		
Cattle (bovine animals) - adult cattle over 2 years	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	82	66	34	3	1	1	1	2	1									1	1												1	1		2	1
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	IVET Graz	Animal	116	95	79	0	1			1	3		1	3	1	1	2	1	2					3	2	2	1	2	3	3	2						

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

Verotoxic Escherichia coli

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin ELISA positive	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O6:H10 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O75:H5 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O75:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O75:HINT - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:H- - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O82:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O82:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O87:H- - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O87:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O87:HINT - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H- - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O96:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC ONT:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H- - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H- - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H1 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H2 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H4 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:HINT - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive			
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	6	4	3	0																														
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - young cattle (1-2 years)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	40	28	13	2								1																	1					
Cattle (bovine animals) - adult cattle over 2 years	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	82	66	34	3								1							1	1	2	1							1			1	1	1
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	IVET Graz	Animal	116	95	79	0	2	1	4	1	2	2	1			1	4	1	1			1		1	1	1	2	1				1	1	1	2	

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

4.5. Tuberculosis

4.5.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 declared bovine herds of Austria officially tuberculosis-free.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria. Sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. Although in spring 2008 infective lung tuberculosis caused by *M. caprae* was diagnosed in one slaughtered cattle. All cattle of that holding were culled following an intra cutan testing showing several positive reactors. Two more cattle holdings with several reagents were culled and some single reactors in contact holdings. In 21 cattle out of 14 holdings *M. caprae* was isolated in 2008. In 2009 again 6 cattle out of 3 holdings were bacteriologically confirmed and in 2010 eight cattle were identified as infected with *M. caprae* and 2011 three cases were found to be positive for *M. caprae*. Since several years a reservoir of *M. caprae* in red deer in an Austrian region has been confirmed and cattle are exposed to the bacteria in the summertime grazing on contaminated pastures in the Alps.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings of *M. bovis* in animals, although *M. caprae* was detected. The two cases of *M. caprae* in humans in 2011 are epidemiologically not linked to the *M. caprae* cases in animals.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2011 a new regulation has been implemented to control *M. caprae* in red deer (BGBl. II Nr. 181/2011). The regulation (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322) obliges the intracutan testings (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) of all cattle and goats that are kept together with cattle in given districts due to the epidemiological situation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

Nil

4.5.2. Tuberculosis in humans

A. Tuberculosis due to *Mycobacterium bovis* in humans

Case definition

Definite: A case with isolation of *M. tuberculosis* complex (except *M. bovis* BCG) from any clinical specimen.

Other than definite: A case that meets the clinical criteria above but does not meet the laboratory criteria of a definite case.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Definite: Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen, Auramin-Rhodamin stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material
- Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC-NaOH and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and MGITmedium.
The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks.
Confirmation of the species by Amplicor (Roche)
- Other than definite: A skin test and an X-Ray of the thorax are performed.

Notification system in place

The person who diagnoses (laboratory/hospital/general practitioner) has to notify definite (M. tuberculosis and M. bovis) and other than definite cases (this excludes radiologists) to the local health authority (Federal Law BGBl. 127/1968: Tuberkulosegesetz, as amended; Epidemiegesetz 1950, as amended). M. bovis is notifiable since 2004 (National Regulation BGBl. Nr. 254/2004: Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The National Reference Center for Tuberculosis (NRC-T) has been nominated since 1995. Since 1998 all data are compiled in a national database.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

M. bovis was not detected in human but two cases of M. caprae were identified; the human M. caprae cases are epidemiologically not linked to the cases in cattle.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

The relevance is inconsiderable.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Annual report of the National Reference Center from 2009 (2010 not available yet):

Table 68 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2011

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Tuberculosis	461	5,49		
<i>M. bovis</i>	0	0,00	unknown	unknown
<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	425	5,06	unknown	unknown
<i>M. caprae</i>	2	0,02	unknown	unknown
M. tuberculosis complex (not differentiated)	29	0,35	unknown	unknown
<i>M. africanum</i>	4	0,05	0	4
Unknown	1	0,01	1	0
Reactivation of previous cases	0	0,00	0	0

Data source: National Reference Center for Tuberculosis as of April 30, 2012

Table 69 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution, 2011

Age group	Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. africanum</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. caprae</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex (not differentiated)		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	7	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	4	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	67	29	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
25 to 44 years	144	90	54	4	3	1	0	0	0	14	7	7
45 to 64 years	114	91	23	0	0	0	1	0	1	5	5	0
65 years and older	89	58	31	0	0	0	1	0	1	9	4	5
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	425	275	150	4	3	1	2	0	2	29	16	13

Data source: National Reference Center for Tuberculosis as of April 30, 2012

4.5.3. Mycobacterium spp. in animals

A. Mycobacterium bovis in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Council Directive 64/432/EEG from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. The monitoring programme is based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection in which all cattle and goats originating from an official tuberculosis free holding have to be tested for tuberculous alterations. A national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all Mycobacteria belonging to the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Specimens are taken from carcasses with macroscopically observable alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis. They are sampled in slaughterhouses and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

All cattle in holdings of designated regions according article 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 2008/322) and published in the Official Veterinary Bulletin were subjected to simultaneous intracutan testing.

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered bovine and caprine animal.

Intracutan testing: All cattle in holdings of designated regions according article 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 2008/322) and published in the Official Veterinary Bulletin.

Type of specimen taken

Organs/tissues: Tissues that are macroscopically altered due to tuberculosis, inclusive lymph nodes (according to Annex 4 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

Case definition

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008 idgF -- Tuberculosis: Infection with Mycobacteria of the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex. Results of the intracutan test: A reactor is each animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive). Doubtful and positive reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008 idgF).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Intracutan testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, as amended and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals in Mödling - After decontamination of the homogenised sample material (2g, homogenised, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörens. Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (heipha/biotest: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37°C ± 1°C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany).

Vaccination policy

Due to the importance of the intracutan tests for diagnostic purposes, vaccinations are prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from official tuberculosis free holding and intracutan tests in animals of given regions according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding. Intracutan tests are performed in animals in holdings of given regions according to the epidemiological situation, defined in the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all mycobacteria belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned.

Loss of the status OTF for the holding from which the animal was originated and for contact holdings. It is prohibited to bring bovines and goats in and out of the holding. Slaughtering of cows and goats can only be allowed by the official veterinarian and has to be performed using a special testing and slaughtering frame. Epidemiological investigations have to be done.

Prohibition of keeping these animals together with animals from OTF-holdings on pastures or market places etc.

Regaining the status OTF:

There must be no animals in the holding showing signs of clinical tuberculosis

All animals are recruited from an OTF-holding

Animals have to be tested according to the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

No reactors are identified after two intradermal testings of all animals in the holding older than 6 months examined earliest 60 days (first tuberculin test) and earliest 4 months (second tuberculin test) but latest 12 months after elimination of the last reactor.

Notification system in place

A suspected case of tuberculosis must be notified.

Results of the investigation

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. Due to the fact that *M. caprae* is endemic in wildlife deer in Western parts of Austria (and South-Western parts of Germany), cattle in this areas has been observed with higher sensitivity.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

M. caprae is differentiated in Austria.

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animal - all animals - at slaughter – Control programme - mandatory - official sampling (all slaughtered animals except those mentioned above)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Samples from suspected swine are taken in slaughterhouses. Sampling is performed when tissue of slaughtered animals is visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye.

Goats in defined regions that are kept together with cattle are subjected to intracutan testing (see chapter *Mycobacterium bovis* bovine animals; Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322).

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered animal

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopic tuberculous alterations and lymphnodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the laboratory

Case definition

Tubercles pathognomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or *Mycobacterium bovis* or *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* or *Mycobacterium avium* isolated from suspected material

Tuberculosis (for bovines and goats which are kept together with bovines): Infection with *Mycobacteria* of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex.

Results of the intracutan test: A reactor is each animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive).

Reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals in Mödling - After decontamination of the homogenised sample material (2g, homogenised, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörens. Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (heipha/biotest: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37°C ± 1°C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

See other chapters.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No need at the moment

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned. Further measures are performed according to Tierseuchengesetz RGBL. 1909/177, as amended.

Notification system in place

The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases in Austria in 2011.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in Austria in 2011.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 70 Bovine tuberculosis in countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing for eradication programme, 2011

Member State: Austria..... Date of the report: 23.05.2012..... Year: 2011.....											
The official post-mortem examination for all slaughtered bovine animals is implemented: Yes											
Region (1)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds * all M. caprae		Routine tuberculin testing		Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds (Annex A(I)(2)(c) third indent (1) of Directive 64/432/EEC)	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination*
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Interval between routine tuberculin tests (2)	Number of animals tested			
Austria	69586	1976527	69586	100	0	0	a) and g)	7865	29	16	0
Total	69586	1976527	69586	100	0	0	a) and g)	7865	29	16	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Use the following letter codes: (a) no routine tests; (b) tests once a year; (c) tests every two years; (d) tests every three years concerning 24 month-old animals; (f) tests every 4 years; (g) others (please give details) Sonderuntersuchungs- bzw. überwachungsgebiet.

* In 2011, 3 cases of M. caprae in cattle were detected: The control program is identical to the program to control M. bovis.

Table 71 Tuberculosis in other animals, 2011

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Mycobacteriaspp.</i>	<i>M. bovis</i>	<i>M. caprae</i>
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	CVS	animal	127,089	0	0	0
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,508	0	0	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,555,567	0	0	0
Cattle*	at farm – animal sampling	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - selective sampling	tuberculin testing in special tuberculosis examination and control areas	CVS	animal	7,865	3	0	3

*TBC-Sonderuntersuchungsgebiete sowie TBC-Sonderüberwachungsgebiete

CVS: Central veterinary services

4.6. Brucellosis

4.6.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. The Austrian cattle, sheep and goat population bears the status Officially Brucellosis Free (OBF) and Officially Brucella melitensis free (OBmF).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Five human cases were identified in 2011. The number of Brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings in Austria, OBF and OBmF

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.6.2. Brucellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Brucellosis cases are reported to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with fever

AND at least one of following seven symptoms:

- Sweating (profuse, malodorous, specially nocturnal)
- Chills
- Arthralgia
- Weakness
- Depression
- Headache
- Anorexia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Brucella* spp. from a clinical specimen
- *Brucella* specific antibody response (Standard Agglutination Test, Complement Fixation, ELISA)

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Serological examination: Serum samples are tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT.

- Bacteriological: Multiple blood samples are inoculated in blood culture broth over several consecutive days. The incubation lasted 4 to 6 weeks, once per week medium is transferred on brucella agar and incubated 5-10 % CO₂ atmosphere (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 56).

- The genus is identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species is identified by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.)

Notification system in place

Notification of Brucellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is OBF and OBmF. All cases reported in Austria are epidemiologically linked to travel in endemic countries or to foreign workers from endemic countries.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This zoonosis has no relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH

Table 72 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2011

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Brucellosis	5	0.06	0	5
B. abortus	0	-	-	-
B. melitensis	3	0.04	0	3
B. suis	0	-	-	-
Brucella spp.	2	0.02	0	2

Data source: EMS as of May 13, 2012

Table 73 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution, 2011

Age group	Brucella melitensis			Brucella not specified		
	all	M	F	all	M	F
< 1 year	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	1	1	-	1	-	1
25 to 44 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
45 to 64 years	1	1	-	1	1	-
65 years and older	1	1	-	-	-	-
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	3	3	-	2	1	1

Data source: EMS as of May 13, 2012

4.6.3. Brucella in foodstuffs

Due to the fact that Austria is OBF and OBmF, food is not investigated for Brucella spp.

4.6.4. Brucella spp. in animals

A. Brucella abortus in Bovine Animals

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds.

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). This means that in the case of dairy herds, the examination of milk samples in accordance with Annex C of Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 can be performed.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Nationwide all bovine milk producing holdings were subjected to bulk milk testing.

In non-milk producing holdings a risk based sampling plan was performed.

Abortion or premature birth: Abortive material and blood of the cow is sampled

Frequency of the sampling

Bulk milk sampling: All milk producing holdings had been sampled minimum once per year according to the regulation (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BgBl II 2007/305). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated.

Holdings without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BgBl II 2007/305). If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out.

- Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood from the cow is sampled immediately post abortion. If the result of the first serological examination was negative, a second blood sample was taken 2 weeks post abortion for serological testing. If this result was negative again, sampling and testing was repeated after two weeks.

Type of specimen taken

Bulk milk

Blood samples

Diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus (stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node.

Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Bulk milk sampling: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BgBl II 2007/305.

Holdings without milk production: According to the sampling plan individual blood samples are taken in the holdings and sent to the laboratories (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BgBl II 2007/305).

Diagnostic slaughtering: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BgBl II 2007/305.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted tissue and blood samples sent to a veterinary laboratory.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be positive for *Brucella abortus*, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a brucella infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get more information about the animal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE.

Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA *Brucella* Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwpSS, OIE ELISAspSS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE *Brucella abortus* Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the IELISA single serum samples were also tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and Competitive ELISA (C-ELISA).

Participation in international ring trials: Participation in international ring trials (Weybridge, AFSSA and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically and serologically as described above.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method. Brucella agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives were used (Oxoid). After inoculation the media were incubated for 4-10 days at 37°C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not allowed (BGBl. 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, § 13 Impfung)

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Control programme according to the National Regulation (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). Abortion or premature birth: Compulsory notification according BGBl 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, §11 Anzeigepflicht;

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions, because OBF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, and BGBl 1909/177, Tierseuchengesetz, as amended

Notification system in place

Abortion or premature birth: Notification of abortions: The livestock owner has to notify each abortion within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the local authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde) (BGBl. 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, § 11 Anzeigepflicht). If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

OBF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Brucella melitensis* in Sheep and Goats

Status as officially free of ovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free (ObmF).

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples were examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. Aborted material and blood samples from the animal were also investigated.

Frequency of the sampling

Principally the sampling was performed during the cold season, between November and May when the animals were kept in the stables.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples according to a sampling plan.
- Clinical cases: Aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or positive serological test result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis (Weybridge and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforth's method. *Brucella* agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4 - 10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The

genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §4, Impfverbot) vaccination is not allowed.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling is performed by the appropriate authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it has delegated this responsibility. Samples are taken in the holdings.

Notification and clarification of each clinical case by bacteriology and serology.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

ObmF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §3, Ausmerzung von Reagenten) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

ObmF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. *Brucella suis* in animal – Pigs

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

According to Guideline 64/432/EEC as amended.

Frequency of the sampling

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples;
- Clinical cases: Abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal; tissues: according to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and abortion material are taken from animals in the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (*B. abortus* used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of *B. suis*.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Due to the fact that a *Brucella suis* antigen is not available, the *B. abortus* antigen is used for the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and the Rose Bengal test (RBT) because *B. abortus* shows cross reactions with *B. suis* antibodies.
 - ELISA and CFT is not available, the *B. abortus* ELISA and CFT are used because these tests show cross reactions with *B. suis* antibodies.
 - Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.
- Bacteriology: Quality control: Laboratory strains
- Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method
 - *Brucella* agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4-10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No mandatory measures but notification is required.

Notification system in place

B. suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.

Results of the investigation

There was no case of Brucella suis in 2011.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to the results of the passive monitoring in pigs we conclude that there is no need for an active monitoring program.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 74 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing (non co-financed), 2011

Member State: Austria Date of report: 23.05.2012..... Year: 2011.....																					
Region ⁽¹⁾	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance ⁽²⁾						Investigations of suspect cases								
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Serological tests			Examination of bulk milk samples			Information on abortions			Epidemiological investigation					
							Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals or pools tested	Number of infected herds	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of <i>Brucella</i> infection	Number of abortions due to <i>Brucella abortus</i>	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of suspended herds	Number of positive animals		Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically
																		Serologically	BST		
Austria	69586	1976527	69586	100	0	0	3776	30572	0	33358	33596	0	907	0	0	1876	47	0	0	1	0
Total	69586	1976527	69586	100	0	0	3776	30572	0	33358	33596	0	907	0	0	1876	47	0	0	1	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Table 75 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme, 2011

Member State: Austria..... Date of report: 21.05.2012..... Year: 2011.....														
Region (1)	Total number of existing ovine/caprine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (2)			Investigations of suspect cases				
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Number of herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of animals positive serologically	Number of animals examined micro-biologically	Number of animals positive micro-biologically	Number of suspended herds
Austria	24216	523900	24216	100	0	0	1570	19014	0	2	0	0	0	2
Total	24216	523900	24216	100	0	0	1570	19014	0	2	0	0	0	2

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Total number of existing ovine/caprine herds: Number is less than in Table 1 (Susceptible animal populations) because mixed farms are deducted from the sum.

4.7. Yersiniosis

4.7.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is not considered a major food borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of Yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.7.2. Yersiniosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Cases of yersiniosis are reported to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following five symptoms:

- Fever
- Diarrhoea
- Vomiting
- Abdominal pain (pseudoappendicitis)
- Tenesmus

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of human pathogenic *Yersinia enterocolitica* or *Yersinia pseudotuberculosis* from a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Faecal (*Yersinia enterocolitica*) or resection (*Y. pseudotuberculosis*) sample material is plated directly on cefsulodin-irgasan-novobiocin (CIN) agar and incubated for 18 hours at 30 °C. Suspicious colonies are identified in an Api 20 E reaction and API 50 CHE reaction. *Y. enterocolitica* is agglutinated with sera against serogroups O:3, O:5, O:9 and O:8. Biovar and pathogenicity are defined.

Notification system in place

Notification of Yersiniosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is the third most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of human cases has been similar in the last years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Yersiniosis is the third most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. Annual report of the National Reference Centre

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 76 Yersiniosis in human - species/serotype distribution, 2011

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Yersiniosis	142	1.69
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	124	1.48
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3	74	0.88
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9	12	0.14
<i>serotype unknown</i>	38	0.45
<i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i>	2	0.02
<i>Yersinia (species unknown)</i>	16	0.19

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

Table 77 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution, 2011

age groups	Yersinia enterocolitica O:3			Yersinia enterocolitica O:9			Y. enterocolitica (serotype unknown)			Yersinia pseudotuberculosis			Yersinia (not specified)		
	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F
< 1 year	2	-	2	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	18	9	9	1	1	-	4	1	3	-	-	-	4	3	1
5 to 14 years	21	13	8	2	2	-	4	2	2	1	1	-	2	1	1
15 to 24 years	7	4	3	-	-	-	6	3	3	-	-	-	2	1	1
25 to 44 years	14	6	8	4	2	2	10	4	6	-	-	-	4	2	2
45 to 64 years	10	4	6	3	1	2	7	3	4	1	1	-	2	2	-
65 years and older	2	-	2	1	1	-	7	2	5	-	-	-	2	-	2
All age groups	74	36	38	12	8	4	38	15	23	2	2	-	16	9	7

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

4.7.3. Yersinia in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2011 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2011“ (BMG-75500/0194-II/2010) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2011, approximately 35,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 75 % of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-dept information. In 2011, nine food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0195-II/B/13/2010). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Enrichment of 25 g sample in ITC-broth and incubation at 25°C for 48 hours and enrichment in PSB-broth at 22-25°C for 5 days; plating on CIN-agar and SSDC-agar and incubation at 30°C for 48 hours.

Results of the investigation

Table 78 Yersiniosis in food, 2011

Food	Sampling stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Yersinia
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant	AT	single	25 g		1	0

4.7.4. Yersinia spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

EU wide harmonized monitoring program.

Notification system in place:

Findings of Yersinia are not notifiable in animals.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in recent years.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has not been investigated.

Additional information

Nil

4.8. Trichinellosis

4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented autochton human infestations since several years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of Trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the EMS. No documented autochtone human infestations in 2011.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Seven documented infestations in food-animals ("wild" wild boars), two of them were imported.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No new measures implemented

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine trichinella meat inspection in pig carcasses

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Trichinellosis cases are reported to the EMS..

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least three of the following six symptoms:

- Fever
- Muscle soreness and pain
- Diarrhoea
- Facial oedema
- Eosinophilia
- Subconjunctival, subungual and retinal haemorrhages

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Demonstration of Trichinella larvae in tissue obtained by muscle biopsy
- Trichinella specific antibody response (IFA test, ELISA or Western Blot)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot

Notification system in place

Notification of Trichinellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The last autochthonous cases have been reported in 1970

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

No relevance in Austria

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 79 Trichinellosis in human - species/serotype distribution, 2011 (EMS)

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unkown
Trichinellosis	1	0.01	1	-
Trichinella spiralis	1	0.01	1	-

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

Table 80 Trichinellosis in human - age distribution, 2011

Age group	T. spiralis		
	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	1	1	0
65 years and older	0	0	0
Age unknown	0	0	0
All age groups	1	1	0

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

4.8.3. Trichinella in animals

A. Trichinella spp. in pigs

Number of officially recognised Trichinella-free holdings

Categories of holdings officially recognised Trichinella-free

Officially recognised regions with negligible Trichinella risk

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

General

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

General

Other: Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered pig

Type of specimen taken

General

Muscles: Diaphragm (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

General

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

General

When trichinellosis is detected with one of the given methods

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Preventive measures in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004, as amended.

The contingency plan in place

Notification system in place

Results of the investigation including description of the positive cases and the verification of the *Trichinella* species

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *Trichinella* in pigs.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Trichinella* spp. in horses

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered horse

Type of specimen taken

Muscles from tongue, masseter, diaphragm and neck.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

When trichinellosis is detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation

No findings in horses.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Trichinella* spp. in animal - wild boars

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about trichinella investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

All farmed wild boars are controlled for trichinella.

Type of specimen taken

Diaphragm muscles (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

When trichinellosis is detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 7 "wild" wild boars (2 were imported wild boars) Trichinella was detected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 81 *Trichinella* spp. in animals, 2011

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
Pigs							
fattening pigs raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system							
fattening pigs not raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	5,555,567	0
breeding animals -unspecified - sows and boars							
Domestic solipeds							
horses	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	1,003	0
Wild boars							
wild	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	22,759	7*
farmed	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	743	0
Foxes							
Badger					animal	18	0
Bears							
Rodents							
Rats							

CVS: Central Veterinary Services

* two cases from imported wild boars

4.9. Echinococcosis

4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Alveolar echinococcosis: Due to the infestation rates of red foxes in Austria (0-40 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Echinococcosis cases are reported to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Not relevant for surveillance purposes

Diagnostic criteria

At least one of the following five findings:

- Histopathology or parasitology compatible with *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *granulosus* (e.g. direct visualisation of the protoscolex in cyst fluid)
- Detection of *Echinococcus granulosus* pathognomonic macroscopic morphology of cyst(s) in surgical specimens
- Typical organ lesions detected by imaging techniques (e.g.: computerised tomography, sonography, MRI) AND confirmed by a serological test
- *Echinococcus* spp. specific serum antibodies by high-sensitivity serological test AND confirmed by a high specificity serological test
- Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *granulosus* nucleic acid in a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- NA

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the diagnostic criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot technique, participant of the UK National External Quality Assessment Service for Microbiology, National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis.

Notification system in place

Notification of echinococcosis according to the Federeal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegeseztz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

- Alveolar echinococcosis has been known in Austria since 1897; annual incidence (1897- 2004): 0-6 cases, mean incidence: 2.4 cases/year (only autochthonous cases); geographic distribution in Austria: mainly in the western provinces (Vorarlberg, Tyrol, Salzburg), but cases have been reported in every province; outbreaks are not known.
- Cystic echinococcosis has been known in Austria at least since 1819; Cases of cystic echinococcosis have been registered in the Clinical Institute of Hygiene and Medical Microbiology (Medical University Vienna) regularly since the beginning of the 1980ies. Annual incidence (1984 - 2006): 20 - 60 cases; mean incidence: 31 cases per year, one third of patients are of Austrian origin; two thirds are from abroad. Geographic distribution in Austria is unknown; a few autochthonous infections could be observed mainly in the eastern and southern provinces (Lower Austria, Burgenland, and Styria); outbreaks are not known.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

- Alveolar echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: fox faeces (contaminated hands and fingers, vegetables, water).
- Cystic echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: dog faeces, presumably in a very few foci (in or around farmers houses)

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Low incidence of both forms of echinococcosis

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria.

Provisionally yearly report published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 82 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution, 2011

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochtone cases	imported cases	unknown
Echinococcosis	7	0.08	5	1	1
E. granulosus	4	0.05	2	1	1
E. multilocularis	3	0.04	3	0	0

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

Table 83 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution, 2011

Age group	Echinococcosis			<i>E. multilocularis</i>			<i>E. granulosus</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	2	1	1	0	0	0	2	1	1
45 to 64 years	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0
65 years and older	2	2	0	2	2	0	0	0	0
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	7	4	3	3	2	1	4	2	2

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

4.9.3. Echinococcus in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all in abattoirs slaughtered animals; the sampling is performed by competent authorities in course of the post-mortem meat inspection; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered animal

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption

Case definition

Each carcass in which cysts, cystic or alveolar hydatids are detected in muscles or organs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Other: All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption were visually inspected, palpated and cuttings were performed

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Post-mortem meat inspection act according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Cystic or alveolar echinococcosis in animals that are used for food production do not play a role for the infection of humans; it is primarily a hygienic problem.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 84 Echinococcus sp. in animals, 2011

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Echinococcus spp.	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	615,153	170			
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	127,089	37			
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,508	0			
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,555,567	3			

All detected cysts are reported but not differentiated

x: Central Veterinary Services, Statistics Austria

4.10. Toxoplasmosis

4.10.1. General evaluation of the national situation

No data available.

4.11. Rabies

4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2011, there was no case of rabies detected in animals in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2011, vaccination programmes were carried out in fox populations in areas of higher risk.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.11.2. Rabies in humans

Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with an acute encephalomyelitis

AND

At least two of the following seven symptoms:

- Sensory changes referred to the site of a preceding animal bite
- Paresis or paralysis
- Spasms of swallowing muscles
- Hydrophobia
- Delirium
- Convulsions
- Anxiety

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following four:

- Isolation of Lyssa virus from a clinical specimen
- Detection of Lyssa virus nucleic acid in a clinical specimen (e.g. saliva or brain tissue)
- Detection of viral antigens by a DFA in a clinical specimen
- Lyssa virus specific antibody response by virus isneutralisation assay in serum or CSF

Laboratory results need to be interpreted according to the vaccination or immunisation status

Case classification

Possible case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Liquor, smears from pharynx, swab from conjunctivae biopsy at the nape of the neck and serum were examined in the fluorescent antibody test (FAT), immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR (Ito M., Itou T., Sakai T., et al. (2001). Detection of Rabies Virus RNA isolated from several species of animals in Brazil by RT-PCR. Journal of Veterinary medicine Science 63(12): 1309-1313.).

Notification system in place

Notification of rabies according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Nil

Table 85 Rabies in humans, 2011

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Rabies	0	0	0	0
Human expose	0	0	0	0

Data source: NRL Rabies as of 26.04.2012

4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals

A. Rabies virus in animal - Wildlife - foxes

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

According to Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung, BGBl II 2010/329: 8 foxes per 100 km² in rabies infected and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100 km² in not endangered and free areas (definition of areas).

Frequency of the sampling

8 foxes per 100 km² in rabies infested and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100km² in not endangered and free areas.

Type of specimen taken

Other: Brain (brain stem or hippocampus)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (e.g. 1 cm²) is examined.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody test (FAT) shows a positive signal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Delivery of vaccine containing baits in the southern part of East Tyrol, Carinthia, Styria and Burgenland; the requirement is 25 baits/km² in an area of approximately 5,620 km².

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung 2010 BGBl II 2010/329, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten

Control of vaccination: Detection of tetracycline in jaw bones of randomly chosen foxes from the vaccination area; additionally an ELISA is performed to proof seroconversion.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Baits-distribution is done by plane; recommendation of vaccination for dogs and cats in the southern border area and public awareness through BMGs (FMH) homepage.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Probably the reduction of the number of the animals (foxes) for investigation.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, and vaccination of the fox population.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Austria is declared as rabies free since 28.9.2008.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. Rabies virus in animal - all animals except foxes

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central nerval symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

Frequency of the sampling

If a case is suspected

Type of specimen taken

Other: Brain (hippocampus and brain stem)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Routinely a sample will be taken from one site of the brain: a part from the hippocampus, brain stem or cerebellum. If an animal has bitten a person then 2 parts from the brain will be taken: hippocampus and brain stem.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Voluntary vaccination of pets.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42;

Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42. If a rabies suspicious pet bites a person, the person is treated.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies.
Vaccination areas, rabies endangered and rabies free areas were redefined.

Table 86 Rabies in animals, 2011

Animal species	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Sampling unit	Comment	Region (NUTS)	Units tested	Total units positive for Lyssa virus (rabies)	Classical rabies virus (serotype 1)	European Bat Lyssavirus 1 (ELB 1)	European Bat Lyssavirus 2 (ELB 2)	Rabies virus, unspecified
Cattle	AGES	Clinical investigation	official sampling	brain	FAT	Animal			7	0				
Sheep	AGES	Clinical investigatin	official sampling	brain	FAT	Animal			1	0				
Goats									0					
Pigs									0					
Domestic solipeds									0					
Dogs	AGES	clinical investigation, bite human	official sampling	brain	FAT	Animal			61	0				
stray dogs									0					
Cats	AGES	clinical investigation	official sampling	brain	FAT	Animal			40	0				
stray cats									0					
Wildlife														
Bats-wild, passive surveillance	AGES	Unspecified	Not applicable	brain	FAT	Animal	found dead		105	0				
Bats-wild, monitoring									0					
Foxes- wild, monitoring	AGES	objective sampling	official sampling	brain	FAT	Animal			2270	0				
Foxes- wild, clinical suspect	AGES	clinical suspect	Not applicable	brain	FAT	Animal			79	0				
Other farm, wild or pet animals (please add the relevant species)														
Badgers	AGES	clinical suspect	Not applicable	brain	FAT	Animal			24	0				
Martens	AGES	clinical suspect	Not applicable	brain	FAT	Animal			30	0				
Other mustelide	AGES	clinical suspect	Not applicable	brain	FAT	Animal			9	0				
roe deer	AGES	clinical suspect	Not applicable	brain	FAT	Animal			8	0				
other deer	AGES	clinical suspect	Not applicable	brain	FAT	Animal			2	0				

FAT: fluorescent antibody test

Data source: NRL Rabies as of 26.04.2012

4.12. Q-Fever

4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation

No information

4.12.2. Q-fever in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.12.3. Coxiella burnetii in animals

Not notifiable in Austria

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for Coxiella burnetii in animals.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic method is the complement fixation reaction, detecting phase 1 and phase 2 antigens. Organs and swabs are tested by real time PCR.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Nil

Control programme/ mechanisms

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Notification system in place

Q-fever in animals is not a notifiable disease

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Q-fever in humans is not a notifiable disease. In Austria the number of sheep per holding is low (3.9 animals per holding in average) compared to countries that have a problem with Q-fever; therefore no change of the epidemiological situation in Austria is expected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 87 Q-fever in animals, 2011

Animal species	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Coxiella burnetii</i>	Number of clinically affected herds
Cattle										
Cattle, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES IVET	suspect sampling	official sampling	animal sample-vaginal swabs, placenta	PCR	animal		2	0	
Cattle, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES IVET	suspect sampling	official sampling	animal sample-blood	ELISA	animal		6	0	
Cattle, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES IVET	suspect sampling	official sampling	animal sample-blood	KBR	animal		441	11	
Cattle, at farm, monitoring				animal sample-blood						
Cattle, at farm, monitoring				animal sample-vaginal swabs, placenta						
Cattle, at farm, monitoring				animal sample-milk						
Cattle, at processing plant, monitoring				animal sample-milk						
Sheep										
Sheep, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES IVET	suspect sampling	official sampling	animal sample-vaginal swabs, placenta	PCR	animal		6	0	
Sheep, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES IVET	suspect sampling	official sampling	animal sample-blood	KBR	animal		83	7	
Sheep, at farm, monitoring				animal sample-blood						
Sheep, at farm, monitoring				animal sample-vaginal swabs, placenta						
Sheep, at farm, monitoring				animal sample-milk						
Goats										
Goats, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES IVET	suspect sampling	official sampling	animal sample-vaginal swabs, placenta	PCR	animal		1	0	
Goats, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES IVET	suspect sampling	official sampling	animal sample-blood	KBR	animal		43	2	
Goats, at farm, monitoring				animal sample-blood						
Goats, at farm, monitoring				animal sample-vaginal swabs, placenta						
Goats, at farm, monitoring				animal sample-milk						
Goats, at processing plant, monitoring				animal sample-milk						

4.13. Clostridium difficile

4.13.1. Clostridium difficile in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

All feces samples or intestines collected in the slaughterhouses in course of the zoonoses monitoring program from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches were forwarded to the national reference laboratory for Clostridium difficile (NRL CD) in the IMED Vienna (AGES) to be tested for Clostridium difficile.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter:

The sampling was distributed by randomization over the whole year 2011.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter: Caecum content of cattle and pigs and intestinal content of 10 chicks per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration a part of the colon (cattle, pigs) or the whole intestines (broiler) were ligated and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbock or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. Remaining feces/intestinal content after their analyses were collected and sent twice a week to the NRL CD.

Case definition

A sample is defined positive after isolation of Clostridium difficile.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The material was directly plated on selective cycloserine-cefoxitine agar plates (C. difficile agar; bioMérieux, Marcy l'Etoile, France), with and without alcohol-shock pre-treatment as described by Borriello and Honour (Borriello SP, Honour P (1981). Simplified procedure for the routine isolation of Clostridium difficile from faeces. J Clin Pathol 34: 1124–1127). Media were incubated anaerobically at 35 ± 2°C for 48 h. In addition, 3–4 g of fecal material was incubated at 35 ± 2°C for 12 days in thioglycolate bouillon (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and then subcultured by plating onto C. difficile agar, after alcohol shock, and incubated as described above. Colonies suspicious for C. difficile (based on morphological criteria, Gram stain results and odor) were tested for the common antigen of C. difficile using a latex slide-agglutination test (C. difficile Agglutination Test Kit; Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK). Strains were stored at –80°C in Cryobank tubes (Mast Diagnostics, Bootle, UK) until further testing.

Toxin detection and PCR ribotyping were performed as described by Indra et al. (Indra A, Lassnig H, Baliko N, Much P, Fiedler A, Huhulescu S, Allerberger F (2009) Clostridium difficile: a new zoonotic agent? Wien Klin Wochenschr (2009) 121: 91–95).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

Findings of Clostridium difficile in animals are not required to be reported to authorities in Austria.

Results of the investigation

See respective tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In Austria, C. difficile is found in animals at very low levels. Therefore the risk of zoonotic transmission for humans seems to be low.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 88 Clostridium difficile in animals, 2011

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive
Broiler flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	IMED Vienna	slaughter batch	341	1
Cattle (bovine animals) - adult cattle over 2 years	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IMED Vienna	animal	489	14
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - calves (under 1 year)	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IMED Vienna	animal	28	1
Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals - young cattle (1-2 years)	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IMED Vienna	animal	185	5
fattening pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling		IMED Vienna	animal	373	1

5. Information on Specific Indicators of Antimicrobial Resistance

5.1. E. coli Indicators

5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and has been continued annually.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs has been implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order Überwachungsprogramme-Verordnung (as amended). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2011 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring are be highly welcome.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Escherichia coli isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal monitoring program „ Durchführungserlass Zoonosenmonitoring 2011 - Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen (BMG-74600/0262-II/B/10/2010)“. The sampling plan for E. coli included cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches.

Type of specimen taken

E. coli was isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle, pigs and broiler. 170 E. coli strains were tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility. The caecum from one cow or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse were collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The national Reference Lab for antimicrobial resistance in the Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of E. coli among the different animal species (cattle, pigs, broiler flocks). All isolated strains of E. coli were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto the MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The process is repeated for colonies which are suspected for E. coli. These colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of E. coli is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Firma Biomedica, Nr. 1069).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

E. coli samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial susceptibility against gentamicin, kanamycin, streptomycin, ceftotaxim, sulfamethoxazol, trimethoprim, ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, ampicillin, chloramphenicol and tetracycline.

Breakpoints used in testing

See respective tables

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables.

National evaluation of the recent situation

Resistance rates in E. coli from broiler are high for some antimicrobials, e.g. fluroquinolones and from pigs for streptomycin and tetracycline. In cattle low resistance rates a found. A census on the use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine is planned.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 89 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of E. coli in animals, 2011

Test method used		Number of reporting laboratory		
Disc diffusion				1
E-test				
Agar dilution				
Broth dilution	x			
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates f		
CLSI		Feedingsstuff		
other		Animals		x
		Food		x
		Humans		x
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested	
			concentration (µg/ml)	
Resistant >	lowest	highest		
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin		> 2	0,25	32
Streptomycin		> 16	2	256
Carbapeneme				
Imipenem		> 0.5	0.125	32
Cephalosporine				
Cefotaxim		> 0,25	0,06	128
Folsäureinhibitoren				
Sulfamethoxazol		> 256	8	1024
Trimethoprim		> 2	0,25	16
Quinolone and Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin		> 0,032	0,008	8
Nalidixinsäure		> 16	2	256
Penicilline				
Ampicillin		> 8	0,5	64
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol		> 16	2	256
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin		> 8	0,5	64

Table 90 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in animals (qualitative tables), 2011

		<i>E.coli</i>								
		Gallus Gallus			Cattle			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		173			172			162		
Antimicrobials:		N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglykosid AB										
	Gentamicin	173	0	0	172	0,6	1	162	0	0
	Streptomycin	173	41,6	72	172	8,1	14	162	49,4	80
Carbapeneme										
	Imipenem	173	0,6	1	172	0	0	162	1,2	2
Cephalosporine										
	Cefotaxim	173	1,7	3	172	0	0	162	1,2	2
Folsäureinhibitoren										
	Sulfamethoxazol	173	30,6	53	172	5,8	10	162	25,9	42
	Trimethoprim	173	15,0	26	172	2,3	4	162	13,0	21
Quinolone and Quinoxalin										
	Ciprofloxacin	173	68,8	119	172	2,9	5	162	4,3	7
	Nalidixinsäure	173	65,3	113	172	2,3	4	162	3,7	6
Penicilline										
	Ampicillin	173	26,6	46	172	2,9	5	162	14,8	24
Phenicol										
	Chloramphenicol	173	5,2	9	172	1,2	2	162	6,2	10
Tetracycline										
	Tetracyclin	173	26,0	45	172	9,9	17	162	54,3	88
Number of multiresistant isolates										
	fully sensitive	173	13,9	24	172	87,2	150	162	33,3	54
	resistant to 1 antimicrobial	173	30,6	53	172	4,7	8	162	18,5	30
	resistant to 2 antimicrobials	173	20,2	35	172	2,3	4	162	21,6	35
	resistant to 3 antimicrobials	173	19,7	34	172	2,9	5	162	14,8	24
	resistant to 4 antimicrobials	173	9,8	17	172	1,2	2	162	8,6	14
	resistant to >4 antimicrobials	173	5,8	10	172	1,7	3	162	3,1	5

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For E. coli this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazol

Table 91 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2011

		<i>E.coli</i> CATTLE																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	172		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N		n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	172	0,6	1						69	88	14				1								
Streptomycin	172	8,1	14									5	75	77	1	1	6	4	1	2			
Carbapeneme																							
Imipenem	172	0	0					148	24														
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	172	0	0				148	24															
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	172	5,8	10											45	67	42	6	2					10
Trimethoprim	172	2,3	4						77	80	11					4							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	172	2,9	5	14	140	13	1		1	1					2								
Nalidixinsäure	172	2,3	4									136	30	1	1				2	2			
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	172	2,9	5								2	51	108	6				5					
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	172	1,2	2									2	57	103	8			1	1				
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	172	9,9	17								23	127	5			1	5	11					

Table 92 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme – active monitoring (slaughter batch) - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2011

		<i>E.coli</i>																					
		GALLUS GALLUS																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		173		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	173	0	0						42	112	17	2											
Streptomycin	173	41,6	72								2	38	56	5	16	23	8	16	9				
Carbapeneme																							
Imipenem	173	0,6	1					153	19	1													
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	173	1,7	3				118	47	5	1			2										
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	173	30,6	53											23	65	30	2						53
Trimethoprim	173	15	26						78	61	8					26							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	173	68,8	119	4	41	9	4	12	53	21	12	1	1	10	5								
Nalidixinsäure	173	65,3	113									47	9	3	1	3	22	40	13	35			
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	173	26,6	46								4	43	73	7			1	45					
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	173	5,2	9									2	53	102	7	1	3	2	3				
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	173	26	45							1	21	100	6				13	32					

Table 93 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2011

		<i>E.coli</i>																					
		PIGS																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	162	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglykosid AB				n																			
Gentamicin	162	0	0					24	108	28	2												
Streptomycin	162	49,4	80										19	56	7	12	29	27	10	2			
Carbapeneme																							
Imipenem	162	1,2	2					111	46	3	2												
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	162	1,2	2				129	28	3						2								
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	162	25,9	42											34	49	33	4						42
Trimethoprim	162	13	21					51	84	6						21							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	162	4,3	7	10	120	25		1	3	2				1									
Nalidixinsäure	162	3,7	6									118	37	1		1	2	2		1			
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	162	14,8	24							4	36	87	11	2	1		21						
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	162	6,2	10								2	50	99	1	2	2	2	4					
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	162	54,3	88							5	64	3	2		1	49	38						

5.2. Enterococcus Indicators

5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and continued in 2011.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of Enterococcus in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs has been implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order Überwachungsprogramme-Verordnung (as amended). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2011 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring would be highly welcome.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.2.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Enterococcus spp. isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of Enterococcus spp. in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal monitoring program „ Durchführungserlass Zoonosenmonitoring 2011 - Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen (BMG-74600/0262-II/B/10/2010)“. The sampling plan for enterococci includes cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches.

Type of specimen taken

Enterococci are isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle, pigs and broiler. 170 E. faecalis or E. faecium strains per animal species are tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility. The caecum from one cow or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse are collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of Enterococcus faecalis and E. faecium in the different animal species (cattle, pigs, broiler flocks). From each sample up to five enterococci were differentiated. Only E. faecalis and E. faecium strains were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The samples are injected into the Citrate Azide Tween Carbonate Agar (CATC-AGAR, Merck Art.Nr. 1.10279) and incubated at 37 °C ± 1°C for 24 h. Then, the medium is left at room temperature for another 24 hrs. Potential colonies are subcultivated on blood agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) for 24 h at 37 ±1 °C which results in the differentiation of E. faecalis and E. faecium through Gram's method, Catalase Test, Arabinose- and Pyruvate-breakdown.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

E. faecalis/faecium samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial resistance against gentamicin, streptomycin, vancomycin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, linezolid, ampicillin, chloramphenicol, synergid, tetracycline, tigecycline and daptomycin.

Breakpoints used in testing

See respective tables

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables.

Table 95 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in animals (qualitative tables), 2011

	<i>E. faecalis</i>								
	Gallus Gallus			Cattle			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	101			129			112		
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	101	1,0	1	129	2,3	3	112	2,7	3
Streptomycin	101	16,8	17	129	5,4	7	112	25,9	29
Glycopeptide									
Vancomycin	101	0	0	129	0	0	112	0	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	101	0	0	129	0	0	112	0,9	1
Makrolide									
Erythromycin	101	58,4	59	129	7,8	10	112	39,3	44
Oxacolidinone									
Linezolid	101	0	0	129	0	0	112	0	0
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	101	0	0	129	0	0	112	0	0
Phenicole									
Chloramphenicol	101	7,9	8	129	1,6	2	112	13,4	15
Streptogramine									
Synercid	101	0	0	129	0	0	112	0	0
Tetracycline									
Tetracyclin	101	57,4	58	129	21,7	28	112	67,9	76
Tigecyclin									
Cyclic Lipopeptides									
Daptomycin	101	0	0	129	0,8	1	112	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	101	16,8	17	129	76,7	99	112	31,3	35
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	101	45,5	46	129	14,7	19	112	27,7	31
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	101	23,8	24	129	3,1	4	112	13,4	15
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	101	6,9	7	129	3,9	5	112	16,1	18
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	101	6,9	7	129	1,6	2	112	11,6	13
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	101	0	0	129	0	0	112	0	0

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, synercid, and tetracycline.

Table 96 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2011

		<i>E. faecalis</i>																			
		CATTLE																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	129	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglykosid AB				n																	
Gentamicin	129	2,3	3									16	106	4				1	1		1
Streptomycin	129	5,4	7												16	89	16	1			7
Glycopeptide																					
Vancomycin	129	0	0						90	37	2										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	129	0	0				3	13	99	13	1										
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	129	7,8	10					38	18	29	34		1			9					
Oxacolidinone																					
Linezolid	129	0	0					1	41	86	1										
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	129	0	0				4	17	72	35	1										
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	129	1,6	2								63	61		3	1	1					
Streptogramine																					
Synercid	129	0	0					3	1	4	3	86	31	1							
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	129	21,7	28					90	10	1				4	17	7					
Tigecyclin																					
Cyclic Lipopeptides																					
Daptomycin	129	0,8	1					4	50	67	7	1									

Table 97 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2011

		<i>E. faecalis</i>																			
		PIGS																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	112	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglykosid AB				n																	
Gentamicin	112	2,7	3							2	7	96	4						3		
Streptomycin	112	25,9	29											1	3	66	13				29
Glycopeptide																					
Vancomycin	112	0	0						67	45											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	112	0,9	1				2	10	81	18				1							
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	112	39,3	44					15	9	30	14	5		2		37					
Oxacolidinone																					
Linezolid	112	0	0						38	72	2										
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	112	0	0				2	6	48	54	2										
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	112	13,4	15								18	76	1	2	7	8					
Streptogramine																					
Synercid	112	0	0								2	62	47	1							
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	112	67,9	76					22	11	2	1			2	33	41					
Tigecyclin																					
Cyclic Lipopeptides																					
Daptomycin	112	0	0			1		3	34	64	10										

Table 99 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *Enterococcus faecium* in animals, 2011

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory		1
	Disc diffusion		
	E-test		
	Agar dilution		
	Broth dilution	x	

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from		
CLSI		Feedingstuff	
other		Animals	x
		Food	x
		Humans	x

<i>E. faecium</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested	
		concentration (µg/ml)		
		Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 32	4	2048
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 128	16	2048
Glycopeptide				
Vancomycin	EFSA	> 4	1	64
Quinolone and Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	> 4	0,25	32
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 4	0,5	64
Oxacolidinone				
Linezolid	EFSA	> 4	0.5	32
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EFSA	> 4	0.25	32
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol	EFSA	> 32	4	256
Streptogramine				
Synercid	EFSA	> 1	0.5	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EUCAST	> 4	0.5	64
Tigecyclin	EUCAST	> 0.25	0.032	1
Cyclic Lipopeptides				
Daptomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.125	16

Table 100 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in animals (qualitative tables), 2011

	<i>E. faecium</i>								
	Gallus Gallus			Cattle			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	72			47			61		
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	72	0	0	47	0	0	61	0	0
Streptomycin	72	11,1	8	47	2,1	1	61	11,5	7
Glycopeptide									
Vancomycin	72	1,4	1	47	0	0	61	0	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	72	2,8	2	47	4,3	2	61	1,6	1
Makrolide									
Erythromycin	72	41,7	30	47	4,3	2	61	49,2	30
Oxacolidinone									
Linezolid	72	0	0	47	0	0	61	0	0
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	72	4,2	3	47	0	0	61	0	0
Phenicole									
Chloramphenicol	72	0	0	47	0	0	61	4,9	3
Streptogramine									
Synercid	72	70,8	51	47	36,2	17	61	95,1	58
Tetracycline									
Tetracyclin	72	54,2	39	47	2,1	1	61	23	14
Tigecyclin									
Cyclic Lipopeptides									
Daptomycin	72	6,9	5	47	0	0	61	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	72	13,9	10	47	61,7	29	61	1,6	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	72	30,6	22	47	34	16	61	44,3	27
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	72	26,4	19	47	2,1	1	61	39,3	24
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	72	18,1	13	47	2,1	1	61	3,3	2
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	72	9,7	7	47	0	0	61	6,6	4
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	72	1,4	1	47	0	0	61	4,9	3

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, synercid, tetracyclin.

Table 103 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2011

		<i>E. faecium</i>																				
		GALLUS GALLUS																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	72	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	72	0	0								10	46	16									
Streptomycin	72	11,1	8											1	50	13					2	6
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	72	1,4	1						64	6	1					1						
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	72	2,8	2				1	2	13	28	26	2										
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	72	41,7	30					5	7	18	12	1				29						
Oxacolidinone																						
Linezolid	72	0	0						5	67												
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	72	4,2	3				2	7	15	27	18	1			2							
Phenicol																						
Chloramphenicol	72	0	0								11	54	3	4								
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	72	70,8	51					9	12	13	21	15		2								
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	72	54,2	39					30	2	1		1	1	3	7	27						
Tigecyclin																						
Cyclic Lipopeptides																						
Daptomycin	72	6,9	5			1			5	26	35	5										

6. Foodborne outbreaks

Foodborne outbreaks are defined as two or more human cases of the same disease or infection where the cases are linked or are probably linked to the same food source. A situation in which the observed human cases exceed the expected number of cases and where a same food source is suspected, is also indicative of a foodborne outbreak.

A. Foodborne outbreaks

System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (Austria = 98 + Vienna) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, food borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food borne outbreaks affecting more than one province that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting:

Since there has not been a coordinated approach for outbreak investigation in most provinces, the large majority (196 of 232) of food borne outbreaks are classified as household outbreaks. Coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - will drastically decrease the total number of outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country:

In 2011, 232 food borne outbreaks affecting 789 persons were reported. 179 persons were hospitalized and 0 persons died. The total number of foodborne outbreaks increased by 20 % compared to 2010. The number of cases affected by an outbreak was 3.4 persons. 13 % (17 % in 2010) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 50 % of all foodborne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n=116), 43.3 % by *Salmonella* spp. (n=100) and 80 % thereof by serotype Enteritidis (n=80).

Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Campylobacter and *Salmonella* pose the most important agents causing 94 % of all foodborne outbreaks, like in 2010. The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

22.7 % of patients affected by these food borne outbreaks are reported as hospitalized (19 % in 2010); there were no deaths (in 2010: 2 lethal cases).

Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of foodborne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

Additional information

The situation of foodborne outbreaks are published in the National Zoonoses Brochure.

Table 104 Foodborne outbreaks with food vehicle identified AND strong evidence, 2011

Outbreak ID	causative agent	agent category	causative agents1	causative agents2	nr. of outbreaks	outbreak type	foreign outbreak	number of human cases	number of hospitalisations	number of deaths	food vehicle	food suspected	food confirmed	nature of evidence	setting	place of origin of problem	origin of food vehicle	contributory factors
2045, 1854, 1853	Viruses	Norovirus			1	general	Germany	82	1	0	Crustaceans, shellfish, molluscs and products thereof	no	yes	Analytical epidemiological evidence	Aircraft/ ship/ train	other	Unknown	unknown
2016	Salmonella	Salmonella spp.	Bovismorbificans		1	general		7	2	0	Pig meat and products thereof	no	yes	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	other	Other	Domestic market	unknown
2435	Cl. botulinum	Botulismus	B		1	household		3	3	0	Pig meat and products thereof	no	yes	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Household / domestic kitchen	unknown	Unknown	unknown
2090	Salmonella	Salmonella spp.	Enteritidis	PT8	1	general		7	5	0	Buffet meals	no	yes	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Restaurant/ Café/Pub/Bar/Hotel/Catering service	Restaurant/ Café/Pub/Bar/Hotel/Catering service	Unknown	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
2188	Salmonella	Salmonella spp.	Stanley		1	general		41	12	0	Buffet meals	no	yes	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Restaurant/ Café/Pub/Bar/Hotel/Catering service	Take-away or fast food outlet	Unknown	Infected food handler
2048, 2064	Salmonella	Salmonella spp.	Typhimurium	DT3	1	general		18	7	0	Buffet meals	no	yes	Analytical epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Household / domestic kitchen	Farm (primary production)	Domestic market	unknown
2148	Salmonella	Salmonella spp.	Typhimurium	DT3	1	general		8	2	0	Eggs and egg products	no	yes	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	other	Household / domestic kitchen	Domestic market	Cross-contamination

Table 105 Foodborne outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence, 2011

		Outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence			
		Number of Outbreaks	Number of Human Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths
Agents categories	Causative agents				
Salmonella	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	7	16	2	0
	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	79	234	78	0
	Other serovars	9	22	7	0
<i>Campylobacter</i>		116	256	49	0
Listeria	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	1	3	3	0
	Other <i>Listeria</i>	0			
<i>Yersinia</i>		2	4	0	0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> , pathogenic	Verotoxigenic <i>E. coli</i> (VTEC)	3	8	3	0
Bacillus	<i>B. cereus</i>	0			
	Other <i>Bacillus</i>	0			
Staphylococcal enterotoxins		0			
Clostridium	<i>Cl. botulinum</i>	2	4	3	0
	<i>Cl. perfringens</i>	0			
	Other Clostridia	0			
Other Bacterial agents	<i>Brucella</i>	0			
	<i>Shigella</i>	1	2	2	0
	Other Bacterial agents	0			
Parasites	<i>Trichinella</i>	0			
	<i>Giardia</i>	0			
	<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	0			
	<i>Anisakis</i>	0			
	Other Parasites	0			
Viruses	Norovirus	5	74	0	0
	Hepatitis viruses	0			
	Other Viruses	0			
Other agents	Histamine	0			
	Marine biotoxins	0			
	Other Agents	0			
Unknown agent		0			

Information on specific microbiological agents

6.1. Staphylococcal Enterotoxins

6.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

6.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 106 Staphylococcal enterotoxins in food, 2011

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Staphylococcal enterotoxins
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		1	0
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		3	1
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	10 g		3	2
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	10 g		2	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		2	0
	at retail	AT	single	10 g		2	0

6.2. Enterobacter sakazakii

6.2.1. Enterobacter sakazakii in foodstuff

Campaign A-002-11: Enterobacter sakazakii in food – infant formula - dried - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January - March

Type of specimen taken

infant formula – dried

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Enterobacter in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

86 samples tested; 0-time positive for Enterobacter sakazakii

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp.

Table 107 Enterobacter sakazakii in food, 2011

Food	Sampling detail	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Enterobacter sakazakii
Infant formula - dried	campaign A-002-11	at retail	AT	single	25	g	86	0
Infant formula		at retail	AT	single	100	g	1	0

6.3. Histamine

6.3.1. Histamine general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

6.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

Not available

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Campaign A-041-11: Histamine in food – Fishery products, unspecified - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - October

Type of specimen taken

Fishery products, unspecified

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Histamin in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

36 samples tested; 0-time positive for Histamine

Table 108 Histamine in food, 2011

Food	Sampling detail	Sampling Stage	Sampling origin	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Sample weight Unit	Total units tested	Total units in non-conformity	<= 100mg/kg	> 100 to <= 200mg/kg	> 200 to <= 400mg/kg	> 400 mg/kg
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	1			1	
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured		at catering	AT	single	10 g		14	0	0			
		Unknown	AT	single	25 g		251	4	0	4		
Fish - raw		at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	0	0			
			DE	single	10 g		1	0	0			
			GL	single	10 g		1	0	0			
		at border control	XX	single	10 g		1	0	0			
			MV	single	10 g		1	0	0			
Fishery products, unspecified	campaign A-041-11	at retail	AT	single	25 g		36	0				
		at processing plant	AT	single	10 g		1	0	0			
			IT	single	10 g		1	0	0			
		at retail	AT	single	10 g		5	0	0			
			IT	single	10 g		3	1	0	1		
			XX	single	10 g		2	0	0			
			ES	single	10 g		1	0	0			
			DE	single	10 g		2	0	0			
			SI	single	10 g		1	0	0			
			NL	single	10 g		1	0	0			
			FR	single	10 g		4	0	0			
			MA	single	10 g		4	0	0			
			PT	single	10 g		2	0	0			
SE	single	10 g		1	0	0						
TH	single	10 g		2	0	0						
VN	single	10 g		1	0	0						
Fruits - products		at retail	GR	single	10 g		1	0	0			
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		at retail	AT	single	10 g		1	0	0			
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		at retail	DE	single	10 g		1	1			1	

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